

Grammatical Failure: Why Liberal Epistemology Cannot Diagnose Indoctrination

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Abstract

Analytic epistemology's treatments of indoctrination, closed-mindedness, and epistemic responsibility presuppose that disagreement reflects agents' differential processing of universally-accessible reasons. Chris Ranalli's *Philosophy of Indoctrination* represents this view: indoctrination can be identified through neutral criteria and overcome through critical thinking, epistemic virtue, and exposure to alternatives. This paper argues that such frameworks rest on false assumptions about language and meaning that philosophy of language rejected in the mid-20th century. Once we accept that meaning is use (Wittgenstein), reference is theory-laden (Quine), and justification is internal to practices (Sellars), the apparatus Ranalli requires – neutral metalanguage, ontology-independent semantics, framework-transcendent reasons – becomes unavailable.

The core argument is semantic: there is no position outside particular frameworks from which to adjudicate between them. What counts as a reason, what registers as evidence, and what appears as a salient consideration are determined by semantic frameworks formed through early socialisation into practices of language use. These frameworks constitute the conditions of intelligibility within which deliberation occurs. They cannot be evaluated through deliberation without presupposing the evaluative apparatus they're meant to generate – the *causa sui* problem applied to semantics. Agency exists in the thin sense that individuals choose between options legible within their frameworks, but agency cannot operate on the semantic conditions that determine what becomes legible in the first place.

This is not eliminativism about agency but precision about its scope. In contexts where disagreement is factual (within shared semantic frameworks), agency and deliberation function robustly. In contexts where disagreement is ontological (across incommensurable semantic frameworks), agency is what statisticians would call a rounding error: technically non-zero but explaining negligible variance. The 'indoctrinated' person and the 'properly educated' person both exercise agency within their respective semantic practices. Neither can

deliberate their way to the other's framework any more than one can translate between incommensurable languages without loss of meaning.

Empirical cases demonstrate this semantic constraint. When linguistic framing shifts – ‘Obamacare’ versus individual ACA provisions, ‘estate tax’ versus ‘death tax’, ‘climate change’ versus ‘climate crisis’ – responses shift dramatically despite identical referents and unchanged factual information. This is not irrationality but frame-dependent semantic activation: different framings activate different aspects of the same ontological structure, producing divergent patterns of salience, inference, and evaluation. Crucially, this operates beneath conscious access. You cannot choose which frame activates any more than you can choose which meaning a word has independent of its use in a language game.

The mechanisms that produce ontological effects – strategic framing that activates particular semantic structures, or intensive re-education that breaks and rebuilds semantic practices – operate at the level of language use, not conscious deliberation. Political consultants understand this: Frank Luntz's focus groups test which framings activate desired semantic responses. But liberal epistemology must code such practices as ‘manipulation’ precisely because they bypass the conscious agency that liberal frameworks privilege. The interventions liberals prefer – education, dialogue, critical thinking – target conscious deliberation, which presupposes rather than produces the semantic conditions where disagreement originates.

Political philosophy treats failures of convergence as agent-level epistemic deficits because it assumes language provides neutral access to shared reasons. But this assumes what philosophy of language denies: that there is a way to step outside particular semantic practices and compare them from a framework-independent standpoint. Davidson's critique of conceptual scheme pluralism applies here: we cannot coherently describe frameworks as ‘incommensurable’ from outside all frameworks, yet from within any framework, alternatives appear not as equally-valid options but as confused, deficient, or incomprehensible.

This creates what appears to be deep moral-political disagreement but is actually semantic breakdown. Conservatives and liberals are not disagreeing about shared facts;

they're operating in partially incommensurable semantic frameworks where what counts as a fact, what patterns of inference are valid, and what considerations have normative force differ systematically. Ranalli's error – and liberal epistemology's more generally – is diagnosing this semantic condition as an agent-level epistemic failure and prescribing remedies (critical thinking, open-mindedness) that presuppose the shared semantic ground that's actually missing.

The paper's implications clarify rather than prescribe. Educational interventions fail not because of poor implementation but because they address conscious reasoning when constraint operates at the level of semantic intelligibility. Moral responsibility mislocates when we blame individuals for 'failing to respond to reasons' that are reasons only relative to frameworks they don't inhabit. Deliberative democracy's faith that discussion can bridge deep disagreement ignores that discussion presupposes shared language games that deep disagreement reveals as absent. These are not political problems requiring political solutions – they're linguistic constraints that political philosophy has failed to recognise.

This is philosophy of language applied to contexts where linguistic breakdown becomes politically salient. The failure is grammatical before it's political. Once political philosophy stops treating language as a transparent medium and recognises that meaning is framework-relative, theory-laden, and practice-embedded, the puzzle isn't why deep disagreement persists despite education and dialogue, but why anyone expected education and dialogue to resolve disagreements that reflect incommensurable semantic practices. Politics doesn't need new theories of justice or legitimacy – it needs to stop assuming the semantic accessibility that makes those theories intelligible across frameworks in the first place.

Ontological and Methodological Position

This paper is written from within a genealogical and grammatical tradition associated with Nietzsche, the later Wittgenstein, and Foucault. Within this tradition, philosophical work does not aim to supply framework-transcendent foundations or neutral criteria of

adjudication. Instead, it seeks to expose the contingent semantic and institutional conditions under which certain forms of reasoning, justification, and agency become intelligible.

I treat ontological frameworks not as metaphysical theories about what exists, but as grammars of intelligibility: historically formed semantic structures that determine what counts as a reason, what registers as evidence, and what appears as an available alternative within a practice. These frameworks are not typically objects of deliberative choice. They constitute the conditions under which deliberation itself occurs.

From this perspective, the aspiration to diagnose indoctrination through agent-level epistemic deficits presupposes semantic resources that are not, in fact, available. The argument that follows is therefore not an internal reform of liberal epistemology, but a withdrawal of assumptions on which it depends.

This positioning has consequences for how the paper should be read. It does not claim framework-transcendent validity, nor does it attempt to compel assent from within incompatible ontological commitments. Rather, it articulates an alternative explanatory orientation that renders intelligible a set of phenomena – systematic remediation failure, persistent mutual unintelligibility, and the marginalisation of certain forms of critique – that dominant frameworks struggle to account for. The explanatory power lies not in universal validity but in making sense of patterns that remain anomalous within liberal epistemology.

Readers firmly situated within liberal or analytic epistemologies may therefore find the argument unpersuasive, confused, or defeatist. That response is anticipated and forms part of the explanatory burden the paper aims to discharge. When critiques of constitutive framework commitments are dismissed without substantive engagement – typically through categorical exclusion (‘relativism’, ‘self-refuting’, ‘nihilism’) – this pattern itself becomes evidence for the semantic incommensurability the paper diagnoses.

The essay proceeds in three movements: first, reconstructing liberal epistemology’s approach to indoctrination and isolating its semantic presuppositions (Section II); second, demonstrating why those presuppositions are unavailable given what philosophy of language established about meaning and justification (Sections III-V); and third, showing that this

pattern of semantic incommensurability explains not only the failure of remediation but also the systematic dismissal of certain forms of philosophical critique (Sections VI-VIII).

I. Introduction

Over the past several decades, liberal democracies have invested heavily in educational and deliberative interventions aimed at improving public reasoning. Critical thinking curricula, media literacy initiatives, dialogue programs, and civic education efforts have all been justified by the same underlying assumption: that persistent disagreement is best explained by deficits in reasoning, information, or epistemic virtue, and can therefore be remedied through improved deliberative practice.

Despite these efforts, many of the most salient forms of disagreement – political, moral, religious – have proven remarkably resistant to such interventions. The failure is not local or episodic. It is systematic. Decades of educational programming have not measurably reduced political polarisation. Exposure to counterevidence often entrenches rather than revises belief. Dialogue initiatives produce temporary rapport but rarely durable convergence. The pattern repeats across contexts: earnest, well-funded, carefully designed interventions that reliably fail to produce the outcomes their architects expect.

I.1. The Puzzle of Remediation Failure

The persistence of these failures suggests that the standard diagnosis may be mistaken. The problem may not lie in the quality of implementation, the sincerity of participants, or the sufficiency of resources. It may lie in the level at which constraint is being located. If disagreement persists despite access to information, exposure to alternatives, and opportunities for deliberation, then the relevant constraint may operate upstream of the mechanisms liberal theory privileges – at the level not of deliberative execution but of semantic intelligibility itself.

This paper argues that the failure of liberal remediation is not best understood as a political or psychological problem, but as a semantic one. Drawing on resources from analytic philosophy of language – most notably Wittgenstein, Sellars, Quine, and Davidson – it shows that the assumptions required for liberal theories of indoctrination and remediation

presuppose a form of semantic accessibility that these traditions have already shown to be unavailable.

The core claim is straightforward. Liberal epistemology's standard approach to indoctrination, closed-mindedness, and failures of belief revision presupposes that disagreement reflects agents' differential processing of universally accessible reasons. But if reasons are not universally accessible – if what counts as a reason, what registers as evidence, and what appears salient are determined by semantic frameworks formed through socialisation into particular practices of language use – then diagnoses of indoctrination pitched at the level of agent-level epistemic failure systematically mislocate the constraint. The failure is grammatical before it is political.

Although often presented as opposed, analytic philosophy of language and genealogical critique share a scepticism toward framework-transcendent foundations and an attention to the contingent conditions under which intelligibility is produced. Taken together, they support a diagnosis in which the limits of deliberation are grammatical rather than motivational, epistemic, or moral. The argument advanced here is therefore not a substantive contribution to political philosophy so much as a diagnostic intervention: it shows that political philosophy's faith in deliberative resolution depends on semantic assumptions that its own intellectual commitments undermine.

I.2. The Semantic Claim

Liberal epistemology's approach to indoctrination presupposes semantic conditions that mid-twentieth-century philosophy of language has already shown to be unavailable: a neutral metalanguage from which to evaluate competing frameworks, ontology-independent semantics that make reasons universally accessible, and the possibility of framework-transcendent justification. On accounts of meaning as use, the indeterminacy of translation, the rejection of the given, and the denial of a neutral standpoint, what counts as a reason, what registers as evidence, and what appears salient are fixed by semantic practices into which agents are socialised.

These frameworks constitute the conditions of intelligibility within which deliberation occurs. They cannot themselves be revised through deliberation without circularity. Once this is recognised, the systematic failure of liberal remediation ceases to be puzzling. It becomes predictable. The constraint is linguistic before it is epistemic, and semantic breakdown becomes politically salient precisely because deliberation is being asked to operate beyond its domain.

I.3. Ranalli as Exemplar

Chris Ranalli's *The Philosophy of Indoctrination* (2024) provides an ideal test case for this diagnosis. Ranalli's account is careful, sophisticated, and internally coherent. It represents a particularly well-developed instance of liberal epistemology's standard approach: indoctrination is diagnosed as an agent-level epistemic deficit – a failure of critical thinking, epistemic virtue, or openness to alternatives – and remediation proceeds through education, dialogue, and the cultivation of reflective capacities.

Precisely because Ranalli's framework is charitable rather than polemical and theoretically robust rather than ad hoc, it serves as an exemplar. If the problem appears here, it is structural rather than accidental. The aim is not to single out Ranalli for criticism but to show that even the most careful articulation of liberal epistemology's approach relies on semantic presuppositions that cannot be sustained once the philosophy of language is taken seriously.

Ranalli's account presupposes three interrelated commitments: that reasons are in principle accessible to properly functioning epistemic agents regardless of background frameworks; that indoctrination can be diagnosed using criteria neutral across contexts; and that agents can, through deliberation, revise even the most fundamental commitments that structure their reasoning. Each of these presuppositions will be shown to be untenable. The problem is not that Ranalli overlooks objections or mishandles counterarguments. It is that his framework requires semantic conditions – shared access to reasons, neutral diagnostic criteria, deliberative revisability of frameworks – that are unavailable given the very theories of meaning liberal philosophy otherwise endorses.

I.4. Roadmap

The argument proceeds in five stages.

Section II reconstructs Ranalli's account of indoctrination and isolates the semantic presuppositions on which it depends. It shows that his diagnosis of indoctrination as an agent-level epistemic failure presupposes a robust conception of agency – one that requires agents not merely to deliberate within frameworks but to author the frameworks themselves through reflection. This is not a marginal feature of his account but a structural requirement. Without it, the distinction between education and indoctrination collapses, and the proposed remedies lose their traction.

Section III demonstrates that the semantic presuppositions Ranalli's framework requires are precisely what philosophy of language has shown to be unavailable. Following Wittgenstein's account of meaning-as-use, Quine's thesis of radical translation, Davidson's critique of conceptual schemes, and Sellars on the myth of the given, it argues that there is no neutral metalanguage from which to adjudicate between frameworks, no ontology-independent semantics that makes reasons universally accessible, and no position outside particular practices from which to evaluate them without circularity. What counts as a reason, what registers as evidence, and what appears as a salient consideration are determined by semantic practices formed through early socialisation. These frameworks cannot be evaluated through deliberation without presupposing the evaluative apparatus they are meant to generate.

Section IV shifts from philosophical argument to empirical demonstration. Through analysis of framing effects – most prominently the divergence between attitudes toward 'Obamacare' and the Affordable Care Act's individual provisions – it shows that responses to identical content vary systematically with linguistic framing despite unchanged facts. This is not evidence of irrationality or bias but of frame-dependent semantic activation: different framings activate different inferential grammars that determine what counts as a reason, what appears salient, and what conclusions feel compelled. The pattern is not isolated but systematic, appearing wherever semantic structures diverge. This provides empirical

confirmation that constraint operates at the level of semantic intelligibility rather than deliberative execution.

Section V relocates agency correctly. It accepts Dennett's thin compatibilism – agency exists in the sense that agents deliberate, choose, and act – but shows that this thin notion cannot deliver the robust agency Ranalli's account requires. Thin agency governs execution within a framework; robust agency would require authorship of the framework itself. The former is real; the latter is unavailable. Using a variance model, the section demonstrates that in cases of deep disagreement, agency functions as what statisticians call a rounding error: technically non-zero but explaining negligible variance relative to the dominant variables of semantic framework and frame activation. Liberal remedies fail not because they are poorly implemented but because they target a variable that, in the relevant cases, does not do the causal work.

Section VI draws out implications. It shows that the education–indoctrination distinction collapses once both are recognised as operating at the level of semantic formation rather than agent-level deliberation. It argues that epistemic responsibility must be relocated from momentary deliberative acts to diachronic formation conditions. It indicates – without developing – that deliberative political philosophy's reliance on shared semantic accessibility faces parallel difficulties. And it acknowledges that the mechanisms which could plausibly shift outcomes (strategic framing, control of formation environments) are precisely those liberal norms code as illegitimate, whilst the mechanisms liberalism endorses (education, dialogue, critical thinking) operate at a level where they explain negligible variance.

The paper concludes by clarifying what the argument is not: not cynicism, not relativism, not quietism, and not an anti-liberal polemic. The aim throughout is deflationary rather than oppositional. No alternative theory is being advanced; no political program is being smuggled in. The argument simply traces the consequences of taking the philosophy of language seriously in contexts where liberal epistemology would prefer not to.

II. Ranalli's Framework and Its Semantic Presuppositions

The purpose of this section is not to evaluate Ranalli's account, but to reconstruct it at full strength.

II.1. Reconstruction of Ranalli's Account of Indoctrination

Chris Ranalli's account of indoctrination is best understood as a normative, agent-centred diagnosis within a broadly liberal epistemic framework. It is neither a crude propaganda model nor a sociological theory of power. On the contrary, Ranalli's project is explicitly concerned with preserving the moral and epistemic standing of persons as autonomous knowers, whilst distinguishing legitimate education from illegitimate forms of belief-formation.

Indoctrination: Definition and Core Criteria

For Ranalli, indoctrination is not defined by *what* is taught but by *how* beliefs are formed and sustained (Ranalli, 2024, Ch. 2). Indoctrination occurs when an agent is brought to hold beliefs in a way that systematically undermines their capacity to evaluate those beliefs on epistemic grounds.

More precisely, indoctrination involves belief-formation practices that:

- aim at belief retention rather than truth-tracking,
- discourage or block engagement with counterevidence,
- and impair the agent's ability to revise or abandon the belief in light of reasons.

Crucially, indoctrination is procedural rather than substantive. This is a significant theoretical advantage: it means Ranalli need not claim epistemic privilege for any particular set of first-order beliefs. A belief can be true and still be indoctrinated; a belief can be false and yet taught non-indoctrinatively. What matters is not the propositional content, but the epistemic posture induced in the learner.

This procedural focus allows Ranalli to avoid collapsing indoctrination into mere disagreement or ideological opposition. Indoctrination is not 'belief I dislike', nor 'belief that happens to be socially harmful', but a distinct epistemic wrong.

Indoctrination vs. Education

Ranalli draws a sharp contrast between indoctrination and education, grounded in the distinction between epistemic openness and epistemic foreclosure.

Education, on his account, is characterised by:

1. exposure to relevant alternatives,
2. encouragement of critical evaluation,
3. and respect for the learner's capacity to revise beliefs.

Even when education is non-neutral in its aims or values, it remains legitimate so long as it preserves the learner's ability to question, reconsider, and potentially reject the taught beliefs.

Indoctrination, by contrast, involves methods that foreclose epistemic alternatives.

This foreclosure can take multiple forms:

1. insulating beliefs from criticism,
2. framing dissent as morally suspect or intellectually defective,
3. or structuring inquiry such that certain questions cannot arise as live options.¹

The distinction, for Ranalli, does not turn on whether instruction is value-laden. All education is value-laden to some degree. The relevant difference lies in whether the pedagogical process respects or undermines epistemic agency.

Why Indoctrination Is Epistemically Problematic

Indoctrination is epistemically objectionable because it violates a core liberal commitment: that persons ought to be treated as capable of governing their own belief-formation in light of reasons.

¹ I borrow the phrase 'live option' from William James, 'The Will to Believe', in *The Will to Believe and Other Essays in Popular Philosophy* (New York: Longmans, Green, 1896), though it has since become common currency in epistemology to indicate hypotheses or alternatives that register as genuine possibilities within a practice of inquiry.

Ranalli identifies several overlapping harms (Ranalli, 2024, Ch. 3):

1. **Violation of epistemic autonomy**

Indoctrination bypasses or disables the agent's rational capacities, treating them as a vessel to be filled rather than a reason-responsive subject.

2. **Foreclosure of alternatives**

By restricting access to competing viewpoints or discrediting them in advance, indoctrination prevents genuine deliberation.

3. **Resistance to counterevidence**

Indoctrinated beliefs are typically maintained through mechanisms that render counterevidence ineffective or invisible.

Together, these features produce a form of epistemic dependence incompatible with liberal ideals of responsible agency and mutual justification.

Diagnosis: Objective Criteria

A key strength of Ranalli's account is his insistence that indoctrination must be diagnosable by criteria that are not themselves partisan or ideological.

To this end, he proposes that indoctrination can be identified using objective, cross-contextual standards, such as:

- whether learners are given access to relevant alternatives,
- whether dissent is permitted and taken seriously,
- whether belief-revision is genuinely possible,
- and whether justificatory practices appeal to reasons rather than authority or fear.

These criteria are intended to be framework-independent in the sense that they do not presuppose agreement on substantive moral or political conclusions. They operate at the level of epistemic procedure rather than worldview endorsement.

This commitment to diagnostic neutrality allows Ranalli to maintain that indoctrination can, in principle, be identified regardless of whether it occurs in religious education, political movements, or secular institutions.

Remediation: Education and Epistemic Virtue

Finally, Ranalli holds that indoctrination is not an irrevocable condition. Because it is an epistemic failure rather than a metaphysical transformation, it is amenable to remediation.

The primary remedial tools he endorses are familiar liberal ones:

- cultivation of critical thinking skills,
- encouragement of epistemic virtues such as open-mindedness and intellectual humility,
- and deliberate exposure to alternative perspectives.

The underlying assumption is that, once agents are placed in environments that respect their rational capacities, they can recover from epistemically defective belief-formation. Indoctrination, on this view, is a correctable deviation from otherwise functional epistemic agency.

Interim Assessment

Ranalli's acknowledgment that indoctrination operates structurally – involving institutional structures, technological systems, and ideological frames (Ranalli, 2024) – does not evade the present critique. The question is not *where* indoctrination occurs (individual vs. institution), but by what criteria it can be identified across frameworks. Structural accounts still require framework-transcendent standards to distinguish education from indoctrination, openness from foreclosure, reasons from rationalisations. Once those standards are revealed as framework-relative, the diagnosis fails regardless of whether the mechanism is interpersonal or institutional.

Taken on its own terms, Ranalli's account is careful, normatively attractive, and internally coherent. It avoids crude propaganda models, resists relativism, and preserves a strong conception of epistemic responsibility. It represents a sophisticated articulation of the liberal intuition that what is wrong with indoctrination is not belief itself, but belief held in the wrong way.

The difficulty, as the next sections will argue, is not that Ranalli misdescribes indoctrination, but that his account presupposes semantic and ontological conditions that cannot be satisfied in precisely the cases where indoctrination is alleged to matter most. Specifically, it requires that ‘reasons’ be accessible independently of the frameworks that make recognition of reasons possible – a requirement that philosophy of language has shown to be incoherent.

But that problem only becomes visible once the account is allowed to stand at full strength.

II.2. The Role of Agency

Although Chris Ranalli does not foreground a theory of agency as such, his account of indoctrination relies on a substantive conception of agential capacity that extends well beyond the minimal compatibilist notions typically invoked in contemporary epistemology. This reliance is not accidental. It is a structural requirement of the framework.

Ranalli’s diagnosis and remediation of indoctrination presuppose that agents are capable not merely of responding to reasons, but of reorienting themselves with respect to the very standards by which reasons are recognised as such. Without this capacity, the education–indoctrination distinction collapses, and the proposed remedies lose their traction.

This becomes clearer once a distinction is drawn between two senses of agency.

Thin Agency vs. Robust Agency

Thin (execution-level) agency consists in the capacity to choose between options presented within an already given evaluative framework. It includes routine decision-making, preference satisfaction, and instrumental reasoning. This is the form of agency typically defended by modest compatibilist accounts: an agent acts freely so long as their actions issue from their beliefs and desires, even if those beliefs and desires are themselves shaped by factors outside the agent’s control.

Robust (authorship-level) agency, by contrast, consists in the capacity to critically assess, revise, or replace the evaluative framework itself. It involves determining what counts

as a reason, which alternatives are salient, and which considerations have normative force. Robust agency therefore requires that agents be able to take ownership of the standards governing their belief-formation, rather than merely operate within them.

Thin agency is compatible with extensive causal, psychological, and social constraint. Robust agency is not. It presupposes a level of reflexive access to one's epistemic standards that cannot be taken for granted.

Why Ranalli's Account Requires Robust Agency

Ranalli's framework does not merely require agents to choose better within an existing epistemic environment. It requires that they be able to recognise that the environment itself is epistemically defective, and to initiate corrective processes on that basis.

For example, remediation through exposure to alternatives presupposes that agents can:

- register those alternatives *as alternatives* rather than as noise, threat, or irrelevance,
- treat counterevidence as epistemically meaningful rather than morally corrupt or conceptually confused,
- and revise not only particular beliefs but the background commitments that structure inquiry.

These capacities do not follow from thin compatibilist agency alone. An agent may be perfectly capable of choosing among options presented to them while remaining incapable of recognising that the menu itself is constrained.

A young-Earth creationist, for instance, may competently evaluate arguments about flood geology versus vapor canopy theory (thin agency) while being unable to recognise 'deep time' as a coherent possibility rather than a category error. What is missing is not responsiveness to reasons as such, but the capacity to revise the framework that determines what counts as a reason.

In this sense, Ranalli's account tacitly presupposes a form of agency that includes authorship over epistemic standards, not merely compliance with them. The indoctrinated

evangelical would need not only to engage with evolutionary biology, but to recognise that ‘what counts as legitimate scientific evidence’ is itself a framework-level commitment that may require revision. That requirement exceeds what thin agency can deliver.

Making the Implicit Explicit

This distinction matters because Ranalli’s liberal epistemic commitments depend upon it. The wrongness of indoctrination, on his account, lies in its interference with the agent’s capacity for self-governed belief-formation. But self-governance here cannot mean mere coherence or internal consistency; it must mean the ability to step outside inherited justificatory structures and evaluate them.

That is a far stronger claim about human agency than is usually acknowledged.

The framework therefore does not merely assume that agents are reason-responsive. It assumes that agents can, at least in principle, author the very space of reasons they inhabit. Without this assumption, the distinction between indoctrination and education cannot be sustained, and the liberal remedies proposed lose their normative grounding. Put differently: if agents cannot author their epistemic frameworks, then ‘educating’ them out of indoctrination is not meaningfully different from ‘indoctrinating’ them into a different framework.

The next section will argue that this conception of agency is not merely empirically optimistic, but semantically incoherent once the nature of ontological frameworks is properly understood.

II.3. Implicit Semantic Presuppositions

Ranalli’s account of indoctrination is careful, charitable, and methodologically orthodox. Precisely for that reason, it offers an ideal case through which to isolate the background assumptions doing the real work. These assumptions are not argued for explicitly. They are inherited, largely without comment, from a broader liberal-epistemic picture of reasoning, agency, and justification. Yet they are indispensable to the framework’s coherence.

This section identifies three such presuppositions. None is idiosyncratic to Ranalli. All are widely shared across analytic treatments of indoctrination, epistemic autonomy, and critical rationality. Together, however, they impose semantic commitments that will later prove untenable.

A. Shared Access to Reasons

Ranalli's analysis presupposes that reasons are, in principle, available to any properly functioning epistemic agent. Indoctrination, on his view, involves a failure to respond appropriately to reasons that bear on one's beliefs or commitments. The indoctrinated subject is not merely mistaken, but epistemically impaired in a distinctive way: they are closed to considerations that should count against their views.

This diagnosis relies on a strong assumption about the nature of reasons themselves. Reasons are treated as standing items, accessible within a shared epistemic space, such that agents may attend to them, ignore them, misinterpret them, or weigh them badly – but not fail to recognise them *as* reasons altogether. When indoctrination is present, the subject's fault lies in their *response* to reasons, not in their inability to register something as a reason in the first place.

The metaphor underwriting this picture is tacit but familiar: reasons as objects in a shared cognitive environment. Epistemic agents occupy the same space; some perceive clearly, others poorly; some avert their gaze, others look squarely. But the objects are there all the same.

This assumption is essential. Without shared access to reasons, the claim that an indoctrinated subject 'fails to respond' loses its footing. There would be no common currency against which failure could be measured – only divergent practices of recognition.

B. Neutral Criteria for Diagnosis

A second presupposition concerns the possibility of diagnosing indoctrination using criteria that apply across contexts. Ranalli's account distinguishes indoctrination from education by appeal to features such as the suppression of critical thinking, the foreclosure of alternatives, and resistance to counterevidence. These criteria are intended to be non-

parochial: they are meant to identify indoctrination regardless of the content being transmitted or the worldview in question.

This requires that the distinction between education and indoctrination be drawn from a standpoint not already internal to the practices under evaluation. The diagnosis must not presuppose the very commitments it seeks to assess, on pain of circularity. Accordingly, Ranalli's framework assumes the availability of neutral evaluative standards by which pedagogical practices can be classified as epistemically legitimate or illegitimate.

Such neutrality need not amount to value-freeness. Ranalli is explicit that epistemic values are in play. What matters is that these values are treated as framework-independent: applicable to agents and practices irrespective of their substantive commitments. The criteria are meant to diagnose indoctrination *as such*, not merely indoctrination-by-our-lights.

This presupposes a metalanguage from which competing epistemic practices can be evaluated without simply reproducing one of them. The diagnosis itself must stand outside the semantic practices it assesses, even if only provisionally.

C. Deliberative Revisability

Finally, Ranalli's account presupposes that indoctrination can, at least in principle, be overcome through deliberative means. Improved epistemic practices – cultivating open-mindedness, encouraging critical reflection, exposing agents to alternatives – are taken to enable revision even of deeply entrenched commitments.

This claim is not merely pragmatic but essential. It assumes that deliberation can operate on the very conditions that make deliberation possible. Agents are not only able to reason *within* their evaluative frameworks but to step back from those frameworks, assess them in light of reasons, and revise them where warranted.

In other words, the framework requires that agents be capable of evaluating the standards by which they evaluate. The criteria governing belief-formation, evidential relevance, and justificatory adequacy must themselves be available for rational scrutiny using criteria that are not simply inherited from the same source.

This is a demanding conception of agency. It goes well beyond the capacity to choose between options presented within a framework. It requires the ability to revise the framework itself in response to reasons that are recognisable as such independently of that framework.

D. Why These Presuppositions Matter

These three assumptions are not optional embellishments. They are load-bearing.

Without shared access to reasons, the diagnosis of ‘failure to respond’ collapses into description of difference. Without neutral criteria, the education–indoctrination distinction becomes framework-relative in a way that undermines its critical force. Without deliberative revisability, remediation through epistemic virtue and critical engagement becomes incoherent.

Ranalli’s account is internally consistent only if all three presuppositions hold. If they fail, the framework does not merely require modification – it loses its diagnostic grip altogether.

The next section argues that these presuppositions are precisely what philosophy of language has shown to be unavailable.

II.4. Why These Presuppositions Matter

The three presuppositions identified above are not ancillary commitments that can be relaxed or revised without consequence. They are constitutive of Ranalli’s framework. Remove any one of them, and the account loses its ability to diagnose indoctrination as a distinctive epistemic pathology. Remove all three, and the framework collapses entirely.

First, without shared access to reasons, the notion of epistemic failure loses its footing. If what counts as a reason is not, in principle, available across agents and contexts, then the claim that an indoctrinated subject ‘fails to respond appropriately’ cannot be sustained. At most, one could describe divergent patterns of recognition or uptake. But failure presupposes a common standard relative to which deviation can be identified. Absent shared access, there is no such standard – only difference. The evangelical who rejects evolution and the biologist who accepts it would not be disagreeing about how to respond to

shared reasons; they would simply be exhibiting different recognition patterns, neither more ‘failed’ than the other.

Second, without neutral criteria for diagnosis, the distinction between education and indoctrination becomes irreducibly circular. If the criteria used to identify indoctrination are themselves internal to particular semantic practices, then the diagnosis simply reproduces those practices’ evaluative commitments. What appears as ‘indoctrination’ will be whatever fails to conform to the diagnosing framework’s own standards of rationality, openness, or legitimacy. The critical aspiration of the concept – to distinguish legitimate formation from illegitimate distortion *across* contexts – cannot be met.

Third, without deliberative revisability, remediation through agent-level intervention becomes incoherent. If agents cannot, through reflection and exposure to reasons, revise the very frameworks that determine what counts as a reason, then appeals to critical thinking, epistemic virtue, or openness are misdirected. Such interventions may improve reasoning *within* a framework, but they cannot operate on the conditions that structure intelligibility itself. The form of agency required for remediation is simply unavailable.

Taken together, these points show that Ranalli’s account stands or falls on a single condition: semantic accessibility. The framework presupposes that agents share access to reasons, that diagnostic criteria can be applied independently of particular semantic practices, and that deliberation can revise the structures that make deliberation possible. If these assumptions fail, the problem is not that indoctrination is rare or difficult to detect, but that the framework lacks the resources to identify it at all.

What follows is not a local objection to Ranalli’s implementation, nor a dispute over emphasis or scope. It is a structural claim: the liberal epistemological approach to indoctrination depends on semantic conditions that philosophy of language has shown to be unavailable. The next section demonstrates this point directly.

III. The Semantic Constraints

III.1. Meaning as Use (Ludwig Wittgenstein)

Meaning is not a relation between words and external objects, nor a mapping between sentences and mind-independent facts (Wittgenstein 1953, §§43, 198). It is constituted by use within practices. To understand the meaning of an expression is not to grasp an abstract entity it stands for, but to know how it is correctly deployed within a language game. This is not a controversial claim in contemporary philosophy of language; it is the settled background against which most post-Tractarian work proceeds.

What counts as *correct* or *incorrect* use is internal to a practice. Criteria of correctness are supplied by the norms governing the activity in which the expression figures, not by correspondence to an independently specified reality. To ask whether a move in a language game is correct is to ask whether it accords with the rules, expectations, and inferential roles that define that game. There is no further, framework-independent tribunal to which such uses can be appealed.

Different language games, accordingly, exhibit different standards of intelligibility. What counts as a good reason, an adequate justification, a decisive consideration, or a terminating explanation varies with the practice in which those notions are embedded. The criteria that govern explanation in experimental physics, moral deliberation, legal reasoning, or everyday practical decision-making are not interchangeable, nor are they reducible to a common core without loss. They are learned as part of participation in the practice itself, not abstracted from it.

This has a direct consequence for the concept of a *reason*. A reason is not a natural kind with a framework-independent extension, available in principle to any properly functioning agent. It is a role-occupant within a normative practice: something that can count as a reason only relative to a background of shared criteria governing what justifies what, what demands further support, and what closes inquiry. To possess a reason is not merely to encounter a proposition with certain intrinsic properties, but to be situated within a practice in which that proposition has justificatory force.

The upshot is simple but easily ignored. If meaning is use, and if use is governed by practice-internal norms, then appeals to ‘the reasons themselves’ as neutral, practice-transcendent items already presuppose precisely what is at issue. One cannot diagnose a failure to respond appropriately to reasons without first fixing the semantic practice in which something qualifies as a reason at all. That fixation is not supplied by reality alone, nor by rationality in the abstract, but by participation in a particular form of life.

Nothing here depends on scepticism, relativism, or metaphysical extravagance. It follows directly from the rejection of the picture of language as a transparent medium standing between agents and the world. Once that picture is abandoned, the assumption that reasons are universally accessible objects – perceptible or ignorably overlooked by any competent agent – loses its footing. What remains is a view on which intelligibility, justification, and rational uptake are inseparable from the semantic practices that make them possible in the first place.

III.2. Theory-Laden Observation (Wilfred Sellars)

If Wittgenstein dismantles the idea that meaning consists in word–object pairings, Sellars dismantles the complementary fantasy that epistemic authority begins with raw, framework-independent experience. His attack on what he famously calls *the Myth of the Given* closes off the most common attempt to salvage neutral access to reasons after meaning-as-use has been conceded.

The Myth of the Given is the idea that there exists some stratum of knowledge – sensory, experiential, observational – that is epistemically authoritative without already standing in need of justification (Sellars 1956). On this picture, perception delivers ‘the facts’, and reasoning merely builds on that secure foundation. Even if language is practice-governed, one might hope that shared experience supplies a common evidential base from which disagreement can be adjudicated.

Sellars’ point is that this picture is incoherent. Experiences do not come already tagged with epistemic status. To count as *seeing that p*, rather than merely undergoing a sensation, is already to occupy a place within what Sellars calls the *space of reasons* (Sellars

1956, §36): a normative network of commitments, entitlements, and inferential relations.

Observation reports are not epistemic primitives; they are moves within a socially articulated practice of giving and asking for reasons.

What matters here is not the details of Sellars' inferentialism, but the structural consequence. There is no observational bedrock that stands outside semantic and normative practices. What counts as evidence, what can legitimately support a claim, what demands further justification, and what terminates inquiry are all determined internally to a practice. Even the most mundane empirical claims presuppose a background of classificatory concepts, inferential expectations, and standards of entitlement that are not themselves given in experience.

This directly undermines a common liberal-epistemological move: the appeal to 'the facts themselves' as neutral arbiters in cases of deep disagreement. Facts do not present themselves as facts except within a conceptual framework that determines what counts as a fact, what kind of fact it is, and what follows from it. To say that an agent 'has the evidence but refuses to acknowledge it' already assumes that the evidential status of that material is fixed independently of the agent's semantic location. Sellars shows that it is not.

Crucially, this is not a claim about individual psychology. It is not that agents are biased, motivated, or emotionally resistant. It is that epistemic status is not attached to items prior to their uptake within a normative practice. The space of reasons is not a warehouse stocked with ready-made justificatory goods; it is a socially instituted space whose structure determines what can count as justification at all.

Once this is acknowledged, the idea that indoctrination can be diagnosed by appeal to neutral evidence begins to wobble. If evidence is already theory-laden, and if observation itself presupposes conceptual participation, then there is no standpoint from which one can simply point to 'the facts' and assess whether an agent is responding appropriately to them without already presupposing the very framework whose legitimacy is in question.

Sellars therefore reinforces the Wittgensteinian result from a different angle. Not only are meanings practice-embedded, but epistemic authority itself is internal to practices

of justification. There is no pre-semantic, pre-normative given that can do the work liberal epistemology assigns to it. Any attempt to ground diagnosis or remediation in such givens is trading on a picture of cognition that philosophy of language and philosophy of mind jointly dismantled decades ago.

The implication is straightforward and uncomfortable. If there is no given, then there is no neutral evidential substrate to which all agents have equal access (Sellars, 1956, §§ 32–36). And if there is no such substrate, then failures of convergence cannot be straightforwardly diagnosed as failures to attend to shared reasons. The disagreement may already be fixed at the level of what can count as a reason in the first place.

Next comes the knife twist: Quine, where even translation itself stops behaving.

III.3. Radical Translation and Indeterminacy (W. V. O. Quine)

If Wittgenstein removes the idea of meaning as reference and Sellars removes the idea of epistemic givens, Quine removes the last remaining refuge: the hope that *interpretation itself* might supply a neutral bridge between frameworks.

Quine's thesis of the indeterminacy of translation begins from a deceptively modest observation (Quine 1960, ch. 2). All the evidence we ever have for interpreting another speaker – whether in a foreign language or our own – is behavioural: dispositions to assent, dissent, act, and respond under observable conditions. From this finite behavioural data, we attempt to construct a translation manual mapping their utterances onto our sentences.

Quine's result is not merely that this task is difficult, but that it is *radically underdetermined*. There is no unique correct translation compatible with all possible behavioural evidence. Multiple, mutually incompatible translation schemes can equally accommodate every observable fact about a speaker's behaviour. Nothing in the data fixes whether a term refers to rabbits, undetached rabbit parts, temporal stages of rabbits, or something else entirely. The evidence runs out long before meaning does.

The crucial point is not the toy example of 'gavagai', but the structural lesson.² There is no fact of the matter about 'correct' translation beyond the interpretive framework we impose. Interpretation is not discovery; it is construction under constraints. We choose among translation manuals by pragmatic criteria – simplicity, coherence with our ontology, inferential familiarity – not because one uniquely matches an independent semantic reality.

This has immediate consequences for any theory that presumes framework-independent access to reasons. If translation itself is indeterminate, then the idea that agents operating in different semantic frameworks are nonetheless responding to the *same reasons*, merely processing them differently, becomes untenable. What looks like 'the same consideration' from within one framework may not even be individuated as a single consideration within another.

Quine also dissolves the notion of atomistic meaning. Sentences are not translated one by one against a neutral background; entire webs of belief, inference, and reference are adjusted together (Quine 1960, ch. 2; see also Quine 1951)³. This holistic picture reinforces the point already made by Wittgenstein and Sellars: meanings, evidential relations, and inferential roles come as packages. You do not extract a reason from one framework and insert it intact into another any more than you can lift a single cog from one machine and expect it to function identically in a different engine.

² The 'gavagai' example appears in Quine (1960), *Word and Object*, ch. 2. Quine uses it to illustrate that even with perfect behavioural evidence, we cannot determine whether a native speaker's term refers to rabbits, undetached rabbit parts, rabbit-stages, or the universal rabbithood. Multiple translation manuals fit all possible evidence.

³ This holism follows from Quine's rejection of the analytic-synthetic distinction in 'Two Dogmas of Empiricism' (1951). No individual sentence faces the tribunal of experience in isolation; entire theoretical structures are adjusted to accommodate recalcitrant evidence.

The role of *interpretive charity* here is often misunderstood.⁴ Charity is not a neutral principle that guarantees mutual intelligibility. It is a methodological imposition from within the interpreter's own framework, designed to make the other speaker maximally coherent *by our lights*. Charity does not reveal framework-independent meanings; it smooths translation by projecting our inferential norms onto alien practices where possible. Where such projection fails, interpretation does not gradually improve – it breaks.

This is the point liberal epistemology quietly hopes never to reach. If interpretation were merely difficult but ultimately convergent, then deeper education, better dialogue, and more patience might suffice. Quine shows that there is no convergence to be had (Quine 1960, §§15-16; Quine 1969). The indeterminacy is not epistemic but constitutive. There is nothing waiting to be recovered once misunderstanding is removed.

Applied to indoctrination, the consequence is lethal. To say that an indoctrinated agent 'fails to respond to reasons' presupposes that the relevant reasons are already identifiable across frameworks and that the agent's uptake can be assessed against a neutral translation. Quine denies both assumptions. What counts as *a reason*, how it is individuated, and what inferential role it plays are all hostage to the translation scheme imposed by the evaluator.

At that point, diagnosis begins to look less like epistemic assessment and more like interpretive imperialism. The evaluator does not discover that the agent is irrational; they discover that the agent's semantic web does not map neatly onto their own. The failure is not in the agent's reasoning but in the assumption that reasoning operates over a shared semantic substrate.

⁴ Interpretive charity is more prominently associated with Davidson (1973, 1974) than with Quine, though Quine's translation indeterminacy sets the stage. The crucial point here is that charity is a methodological constraint from within the interpreter's framework, not a discovery procedure for framework-independent meanings.

Quine therefore completes the erosion begun by Wittgenstein and Sellars (Quine 1969, 'Epistemology Naturalized'). There is no neutral meaning, no given evidence, and now no neutral translation. Cross-framework engagement is always mediated by interpretive choices internal to the evaluator's own ontology. The hope that disagreement can be adjudicated by appeal to shared reasons collapses not because agents are stubborn or malicious, but because the semantic machinery required for such adjudication never existed.

Next comes the delicate part: Davidson,⁵ who appears to deny incommensurability whilst quietly entrenching it in lived form.

III.4. The Conceptual Scheme Problem (Donald Davidson)

Davidson is the point at which lazy readers panic and shout 'Aha, so there are *no* conceptual schemes', as if that settles anything. What Davidson actually does is more awkward and, for your purposes, more useful: he blocks the *God's-eye* description of incommensurable schemes, whilst leaving intact the lived reality of asymmetric intelligibility.

Davidson's critique targets a certain picture of conceptual schemes: the idea that there are multiple, mutually incommensurable 'frameworks' organising experience, which

⁵ The roles of Quine and Davidson in this argument are distinct and complementary. Quine establishes the underdetermination of translation: behavioural evidence never fixes a unique mapping between semantic schemes, undermining the idea of framework-independent access to reasons. Davidson, by contrast, targets the coherence of neutral comparison: he rejects the idea that multiple conceptual schemes can be surveyed or adjudicated from a standpoint outside all schemes. Nothing in Davidson's critique restores a neutral metalanguage or framework-transcendent semantics. On the contrary, it blocks precisely the external standpoint liberal epistemology presupposes. The present argument relies on Quine for underdetermination and Davidson for the impossibility of neutral adjudication, not on any thesis of symmetric, absolute incommensurability.

can be compared from some standpoint that is neutral with respect to all of them (Davidson 1973).⁶ The problem is that the very act of identifying a scheme as a scheme seems to require translation and interpretation, and interpretation requires finding enough shared structure to make sense of the other as a believer, speaker, and reasoner at all. If you can interpret them, Davidson suggests, you have already located substantial common ground. If you cannot, you are not dealing with an alternative scheme, but with noise.

So yes: the strong, museum-display version of incommensurability gets into trouble (Davidson 1973, pp. 6-7). If you claim, from nowhere, that two schemes are untranslatable, you have tacitly assumed precisely the standpoint your own claim declares impossible. That is Davidson's central pressure: *you cannot coherently take up a position outside all schemes in order to compare schemes as objects*. The fantasy of a neutral meta-language is not rescued by renaming it 'conceptual scheme theory'.

But the inference many then make is a non sequitur: therefore deep disagreement is illusory; therefore commensurability reigns; therefore deliberation is safe again. Davidson does not entitle you to that comfort.⁷

What Davidson really forces is a re-description. The mistake is not in noticing that there are systematic breakdowns in mutual intelligibility. The mistake is in imagining those breakdowns can be captured as a clean, symmetric relation between two conceptual

⁶ Davidson (1973), 'On the Very Idea of a Conceptual Scheme', *Proceedings and Addresses of the American Philosophical Association* 47: 5-20. The title itself signals Davidson's scepticism toward the conceptual scheme picture, though the implications are often misread as a refutation of all framework-relative constraints.

⁷ This misreading of Davidson is common in analytic epistemology, where 'Davidson refuted incommensurability' functions as a conversation-stopper. For a more careful reading that preserves the phenomenon Davidson's argument actually targets, see Rorty (1979), ch. 6, and McDowell (1994), Lecture III.

schemes, described from a third position. Once you drop that third position, you do not thereby obtain harmony. You obtain asymmetry.

Here is the pivot your argument needs: from within any functioning framework, alternative frameworks do not typically appear as equally live options. They appear as confused, morally perverse, intellectually unserious, or simply not *about* the same thing. In other words, the barrier is not best modelled as ‘two languages with no translation’. It is modelled as ‘one language in which the other is rendered as error’.

That is not a view-from-nowhere claim. It is a phenomenological and grammatical claim about how intelligibility operates from within a practice. A framework supplies criteria of sense. Those criteria do not merely sort true from false; they sort sense from nonsense, reason from rationalisation, evidence from propaganda, education from indoctrination. The same ‘content’ is not merely evaluated differently across frameworks. It is *typed* differently.

This is why Davidson is a gift rather than an obstacle. He compels you to avoid the naïve posture of declaring incommensurability as an external diagnosis. Instead, you describe the structure of mutual misunderstanding in the only place it can actually be observed: in the internal operation of semantic practices.

On this picture:

- We cannot coherently stand outside all frameworks to compare them as schemes.
- Yet within any given framework, rival frameworks are not encountered as neutral alternatives.
- They are encountered as defective, irrational, or unintelligible, because the framework’s grammar supplies the standards by which ‘alternative’ would have to be recognised as such.

So the asymmetry is lived, not surveyed.⁸ And that is precisely what liberal deliberative optimism tends to miss: it imagines disagreement as a contest over shared reasons, rather than a conflict over the very grammar that determines what can count as a reason in the first place.

This also anticipates the predictable complaint: 'But I can understand you well enough to disagree with you, so we must share a scheme'. Fine. You can *partially* translate across boundaries, and you can often achieve enough overlap to argue. But Davidson never claims that partial translation eliminates the deeper fact: translation is carried out under the constraints of charity and coherence as determined by the interpreter's own norms (Davidson 1973, pp. 18-20; Davidson 1974).⁹ What survives translation is what can be made to fit. What does not fit is either domesticated, reclassified, or rejected. That is not neutral access; it is interpretive capture.

Which brings you neatly to the synthesis: once Wittgenstein, Sellars, Quine, and Davidson are taken together, the promise of neutral semantic accessibility is not merely unfulfilled. It is conceptually incoherent.

⁸ This does not entail that all frameworks are hermetically sealed or that persuasion is impossible. It entails that persuasion, where it occurs, operates not through neutral reason-presentation but through processes (frame activation, immersion in alternative practices, gradual semantic drift) that liberal epistemology prefers not to acknowledge. The constraint is not absolute but systematic.

⁹ Davidson develops the principle of interpretive charity most explicitly in 'Belief and the Basis of Meaning' (1974), *Synthese* 27(3-4): 309-323. Charity requires maximizing agreement and rationality by the interpreter's lights, which means translation inevitably projects the interpreter's norms onto the interpreted.

III.5. Synthesis: No Neutral Metalanguage

By *ontological framework* I do not mean a catalogue of metaphysical commitments, as though the problem were simply that people disagree about what entities exist. I mean something both more deflationary and more operational: the semantic–grammatical structures that determine what can count as a reason, what registers as salient, and what even shows up as an available alternative within a practice of language use. The ‘ontological’ here is not a theory of Being, but the background of intelligibility itself.

At this point the individual results should already be exerting pressure on one another. All that remains is to stop treating them as modular insights that can be acknowledged independently, and to take seriously what follows once they are held together.

From Wittgenstein, meaning is use. What words, reasons, and standards mean is fixed by their role within rule-governed practices, not by correspondence to framework-independent objects. Correctness is internal to a practice; it is not imposed from outside it.

From Sellars, there is no epistemic given. What registers as observation or evidence already presupposes conceptual and normative participation in the space of reasons. There is no neutral evidential substrate upon which disagreement can be adjudicated prior to such participation.

From Quine, translation is radically underdetermined. Behavioural evidence never fixes a unique mapping between vocabularies or conceptual repertoires. Interpretation is not the discovery of framework-independent meanings, but the imposition of structure guided by the interpreter’s own theoretical commitments. Meaning does not survive intact across translation; it is reconstructed under constraint.

From Davidson, comparison without a standpoint is incoherent. There is no view from nowhere from which conceptual schemes can be surveyed and adjudicated. Whatever intelligibility is achieved occurs from within a framework that supplies the very standards by which sense, belief, and reasonhood are recognised.

Taken together, these results collapse a familiar liberal aspiration. There is no neutral metalanguage from which competing frameworks can be assessed. No standpoint outside

practice from which we can say, without remainder, which reasons are *the* real ones, which standards are objectively appropriate, or which beliefs are properly responsive to evidence.

What counts as a reason, what registers as evidence, what appears salient or marginal, what looks like education rather than indoctrination – these are not fixed independently of semantic practice. They are determined by the background grammar that governs what can count as justification, what demands further support, and what terminates inquiry. This is not because frameworks are ineffable, sealed off, or metaphysically exotic. It is because meaning is embedded in practice, and practice supplies its own criteria of intelligibility.

It is in this sense that *ontological frameworks* should be understood here. The term does not name a catalogue of metaphysical commitments about what entities exist, nor neatly bounded conceptual schemes operating uniformly across all domains. It names domain-specific semantic-grammatical structures that determine what can count as a reason, what even shows up as an available alternative, and which inferential transitions feel obligatory, optional, or nonsensical. To inhabit a framework is not primarily to endorse a set of propositions, but to have learned how to go on with words in a way that renders some moves intelligible and others defective, confused, or out of bounds altogether.

A single agent can participate in multiple frameworks – professional, domestic, political – without this entailing reflective access to the grammatical differences between them. Cross-framework movement is ubiquitous; what is not ubiquitous is awareness that movement has occurred. Framework boundaries become visible only when inferential expectations clash: when what counts as a reason in one domain fails to register as such in another, when a standard continuation in one practice appears as non sequitur or category error in another. Frameworks are thus individuated not by sharp metaphysical boundaries but by patterns of inferential breakdown: the points at which reasoning that feels natural in one practice generates confusion, resistance, or misrecognition in another.

This is why disagreement at the framework level does not present itself as a dispute between equally live options. From within any given practice, rival frameworks are not

typically encountered as neutral alternatives awaiting evaluation. They appear instead as confusion, distortion, bad faith, category error, perversity, or pathology. The asymmetry is not surveyed from an external vantage; it is lived from within the grammar that supplies criteria of sense. Davidson blocks the fantasy of describing this asymmetry from nowhere. He does not eliminate the asymmetry itself.

Once this is seen, a further liberal hope quietly dissolves. Liberal epistemology wants shared reasons without shared grammar. Neutral diagnosis without neutral ground. Deliberation that somehow operates on the very conditions that make deliberation possible. But once the philosophy of language is taken seriously – really taken seriously – these aspirations are revealed as category mistakes.

There is no higher court of appeal. No semantic umpire hovering above the game. Frameworks do not meet on neutral ground; they collide from within their own grammars. And when one framework judges another, it does so using standards the other may not even recognise as standards at all.

This is not an optional add-on to the argument. It is the load-bearing structure beneath everything that follows. If there is no neutral metalanguage, then any theory of indoctrination that presupposes shared access to reasons, framework-independent diagnostic criteria, or deliberative revision of the conditions of intelligibility has already smuggled its conclusion into its premises.

What remains is not to ask whether agents can deliberate better, but to ask how deliberation could possibly get its authority over the very conditions that make deliberation intelligible at all. That question is unavoidable – and it leads directly to the next problem liberal epistemology cannot afford to face.

III.6. The Causa Sui Problem Applied to Semantics

At this stage, the remaining liberal escape route is predictable: *just step back and reflect*. If a framework is distorting one's epistemic life, the agent can supposedly evaluate it,

revise it, or exit it through deliberation. The problem is that this instruction presupposes precisely what is in question.

To evaluate a framework, one needs criteria. But criteria are not freestanding instruments; they are supplied by a framework. Standards of coherence, relevance, evidential sufficiency, rational responsiveness – these are not neutral tools one picks up prior to practice. They are internal to practices of justification.

This creates a structural regress:

- To assess a framework, you need evaluative standards.
- Those standards are generated within a framework.
- Any attempt to assess the framework therefore presupposes the very apparatus whose legitimacy is under scrutiny.

There is no way to perform the evaluation without already standing somewhere. Reflection does not float above semantic practice; it operates inside it. The instruction to ‘step back’ merely redescribes an intra-framework manoeuvre as if it were a framework-transcendent one.

The consequence is not infinite regress in the abstract, but vicious circularity in practice. The circle cannot be escaped because the circle is not an error; it is the condition of intelligibility. One cannot bootstrap oneself into a neutral position any more than one can lift oneself by one’s own shoelaces. Semantic frameworks do not emerge from reflection; reflection is one of the things they make possible.

This is where the analogy with the *causa sui* problem becomes instructive. Just as a subject cannot be the ultimate author of the will that authors its actions, a semantic agent cannot be the ultimate author of the criteria by which their own framework is evaluated.¹⁰

¹⁰ The *causa sui* argument is developed in Strawson (1994), ‘The Impossibility of Moral Responsibility’, *Philosophical Studies* 75(1-2): 5-24. Strawson argues that true moral responsibility requires being the ultimate cause of one’s own character and desires – which

The demand that agents freely revise their most fundamental commitments through deliberation mirrors the demand that agents be self-caused in Strawson's sense. Both demands collapse under the same structural impossibility.¹¹

What follows is decisive for liberal epistemology. If frameworks supply the conditions under which reasons count as reasons, then deliberation cannot operate on those conditions without presupposing them. There is no meta-deliberation capable of adjudicating between frameworks using criteria that are not already framework-relative. Appeals to reflection, openness, or epistemic virtue simply recycle the problem at a higher rhetorical pitch.

This does not show that frameworks are immutable or eternal. It shows something more uncomfortable: their revision is not a deliberative achievement of individual agents. Change occurs, but not by way of the mechanisms liberal epistemology prefers to acknowledge. That point will matter later. For now, the conclusion is narrower and more lethal.

The injunction to 'just step back and reflect' is not a solution. It is a grammatical error.

requires authoring the will that authors one's will, ad infinitum. The regress is vicious: you cannot bootstrap yourself into being self-caused. The present argument applies this structure to semantic frameworks: agents cannot deliberate themselves into the semantic conditions that make deliberation possible, as this requires presupposing the evaluative apparatus deliberation is meant to generate.

¹¹ See Galen Strawson, *Freedom and Belief* (1986); "The Impossibility of Moral Responsibility" (1994); and the formulation of the Basic Argument in *Freedom and Resentment*—era debates. Whilst Strawson's target is ultimate moral responsibility, the structural point generalises: evaluative revision presupposes evaluative machinery, yielding a vicious regress when applied to the machinery itself.

III.7 Why Certain Arguments Do Not Land: The Meta-Explanatory Payoff

One of the advantages of treating ontological frameworks as semantic structures is that it explains not only the persistence of deep disagreement, but a further, often overlooked phenomenon: the systematic failure of certain kinds of critique to register at all. Some arguments do not merely fail to persuade; they fail to be processed as arguments. They are dismissed as confused, self-refuting, incoherent, unserious, or ‘not really philosophy’ before their content is engaged.¹² This pattern is not accidental, and it is not confined to political disagreement.

From within a prevailing framework, challenges to framework-constitutive assumptions are not encountered as rival positions. They appear instead as category errors. The rejection masquerades as an assessment of quality, but it is better understood as a boundary-maintenance operation: the framework renders certain moves illegible as moves.

This helps explain a long-standing puzzle in academic philosophy. Relativist and quietist arguments have been developed with considerable sophistication over decades. They are not naïve, casual, or under-argued. Yet they rarely ‘land’ within mainstream analytic discourse. The standard responses are strikingly formulaic: *self-refuting*, *gives up on truth*, *confuses semantics with metaphysics*, *abandons rationality*. These verdicts are typically delivered without sustained engagement with the internal logic of the arguments in question.

¹² This is not a circular manoeuvre (‘this theory predicts you’ll reject it, therefore rejections confirm it’). The claim is more specific: IF (1) frameworks determine criteria of intelligibility, and (2) this paper challenges framework-constitutive assumptions, THEN (3) dismissals through categorical exclusion (‘relativism’, ‘self-refuting’) are evidence for (1) rather than refutations of it. The prediction is falsifiable: if critiques were engaged substantively rather than dismissed categorically, that would count against the framework-relativity thesis. The actual pattern of dismissal without engagement is what the semantic account predicts and psychological/moral accounts struggle to explain.

The category 'relativism' already functions, within the prevailing ontology, as a marker of philosophical failure. Once applied, it forecloses further uptake.

The same is true of quietist readings of Wittgenstein. Interpreting philosophy as an activity that dissolves rather than solves certain problems is not treated as a substantive philosophical position but as a refusal to do philosophy at all. Within a framework where philosophy is tacitly defined as theory construction, systematic explanation, or foundation-laying, quietism is unintelligible except as abdication. It is therefore marginalised, domesticated, or re-described until it fits a more familiar mould. Again, this is not a rebuttal on the merits; it is a semantic exclusion.

What matters is not whether one endorses relativism or quietism. The point is structural. Arguments that call into question the very criteria by which arguments are recognised as such will not be evaluated by those criteria. They will be screened out in advance. No amount of additional clarification, precision, or evidence helps, because the failure is not local. The argument does not satisfy the conditions for counting as an argument within that practice.

This pattern is not unique to philosophy. Kuhn's analysis of scientific revolutions made the same point in a different register.¹³ Paradigm-challenging theories are not rejected because the data are insufficient; they are rejected because the data do not yet *count as data* within the existing paradigm. What appears retrospectively as obstinacy or dogmatism is, in situ, a matter of semantic fit. The new framework does not initially provide intelligible continuations of the old one's inferential practices, so it cannot be recognised as legitimate science until a broader reorganisation has occurred.

¹³ Kuhn (1962), *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. For Kuhn, paradigm-challenging theories are rejected not due to insufficient data but because data don't yet count as data within existing paradigms – a process he terms 'incommensurability'.

Seen in this light, the reception of critiques of liberal epistemology follows a familiar pattern. Arguments that deny the availability of framework-neutral reasons, that locate constraint at the level of semantic formation rather than conscious choice, or that treat autonomy as a regulative fiction rather than a metaphysical fact, are not rebutted so much as *mis-typed*. They are labelled defeatist, cynical, relativist, or politically motivated. These labels do not describe the arguments; they perform the work of rendering them unintelligible within a framework that requires the very assumptions under challenge in order to function.

This gives the present account a distinctive meta-explanatory advantage. It explains not only why liberal remedies for indoctrination systematically fail, but also why critiques of those remedies predictably fail to gain traction. The framework predicts its own reception. If the argument were to be widely absorbed within liberal epistemology without friction, that would count against it. The fact that it is more likely to be dismissed through familiar categorical exclusions is not a weakness but a confirmation of the diagnosis.

The same structure appears wherever deeply entrenched practices collide: between analytic and continental philosophy, across disciplinary boundaries, in professional disputes, in religious–secular conflicts, and in generational or cultural divides. In each case, the problem is not primarily one of insufficient goodwill, intelligence, or information. It is that the semantic conditions that make reasons recognisable are not shared. When those conditions diverge, some utterances cease to function as candidates for agreement or disagreement at all.

Once this is seen, the failure of certain arguments to ‘land’ no longer appears mysterious or conspiratorial. It is the ordinary operation of semantic frameworks protecting their own conditions of intelligibility. What looks like gatekeeping or bad faith is often something more mundane and more intractable: a grammar that cannot accommodate the move being attempted.

IV. Semantic Breakdown in Practice: The Framing Evidence

IV.1. Frame-Dependent Semantic Activation

Framing effects are typically treated as psychological artefacts: cognitive biases that distort an otherwise neutral process of information uptake and rational evaluation. On this view, frames interfere with reasoning by selectively highlighting features of a situation, thereby skewing judgment away from what an ideally rational agent would conclude under conditions of full information and reflective equilibrium.

This interpretation mislocates the phenomenon. Framing effects are not distortions of a neutral semantic baseline. They are manifestations of the semantic structures that constitute ontological frameworks. What varies across frames is not merely attention or emphasis, but the inferential grammar that determines what can count as a reason, what registers as salient, and which evaluative transitions feel natural or compulsory. The psychological effects are downstream of the semantic organisation, not the other way around.

Work on political framing and metaphor, most prominently associated with George Lakoff, is best understood in this light (Lakoff 2002; Lakoff & Johnson 1980). Lakoff's central insight is not that people are irrationally swayed by rhetoric, but that conceptual metaphors and frames organise domains of reasoning by structuring patterns of inference. Frames are not optional overlays placed atop an independently intelligible reality; they are part of the machinery that makes that reality intelligible in the first place.

There is a revealing tension in Lakoff's own work that illustrates the difficulty of escaping liberal presuppositions even when the evidence points away from them. Lakoff-theorist demonstrates, through careful linguistic analysis, that conceptual metaphors and frames are constitutive of intelligibility. They are not decorative features layered atop a neutral semantic core, but the machinery through which domains of experience become cognitively organised. Frames determine what counts as a relevant consideration, what inferences feel natural, and what conclusions appear compelling. They are formed through deep socialisation into linguistic practices and remain remarkably stable across contexts.

But Lakoff-the-activist, particularly in his prescriptive political work, proceeds as if none of this were true. In *Don't Think of an Elephant!* and subsequent advice to progressive causes, Lakoff recommends that liberals 'reframe the issues', 'use better metaphors', and 'avoid activating conservative frames' (Lakoff 2004). The implication is clear: frames are tools that can be strategically selected, adopted, or discarded through deliberate rhetorical choice. Activists are counselled to 'think carefully about framing' before entering public debate, as though framing were an optional overlay on an otherwise neutral message rather than the condition of that message's intelligibility.

This prescription flatly contradicts the descriptive research. If frames are constitutive of intelligibility and formed through long-term immersion in linguistic practices, then the injunction to 'just reframe' is structurally incoherent. It asks agents to operate at a level their own cognition cannot access. Frame activation is precognitive; one does not first grasp content neutrally and then select a frame through which to present it. The frame is already operative by the time deliberation begins. To tell someone 'don't think of an elephant' is not merely ineffective; it presupposes a kind of voluntary semantic control that Lakoff's own research shows to be unavailable.

The tension is not a minor inconsistency. It reveals the grip of liberal assumptions even on a theorist whose empirical work systematically undermines them. Lakoff cannot consistently follow his descriptive findings to their logical conclusion because doing so would require abandoning the premise that frames can be revised through the kind of agent-level intervention that liberal epistemology privileges. The advice must be given, even though the research shows it cannot work. The framework – liberal, deliberative, committed to rational persuasion – requires it.

Contrast this with the approach of Republican strategist Frank Luntz. Luntz's focus-group testing of terms like 'death tax' versus 'estate tax', 'climate change' versus 'global warming', or 'healthcare reform' versus 'government takeover' was not an attempt to change

frames.¹⁴ It was an attempt to identify which terms most effectively activate existing conservative semantic structures. The goal was not to persuade across frameworks but to optimise triggering within a framework. When Luntz discovered that ‘death tax’ produced stronger opposition than ‘estate tax’ among conservative respondents, he was not discovering a rhetorical trick. He was discovering that the term activated a semantic field – loss, death, government intrusion at a moment of vulnerability – already operative within conservative grammar.

Luntz’s strategy works precisely because it does not attempt what Lakoff’s advice attempts. Luntz activates existing structures; Lakoff’s prescriptions try to transform them. The former is semantically possible; the latter is not. This is why, over the past three decades, conservative messaging has consistently outperformed progressive messaging despite progressives having access to Lakoff’s sophisticated theoretical apparatus. The asymmetry is not a matter of talent, funding, or messaging competence. It is a function of structural possibility.

The point is not that Luntz is more insightful than Lakoff. It is that Luntz’s goals are achievable within semantic constraints whilst Lakoff’s are not. And the reason Lakoff cannot see this – or cannot consistently act on it – is that recognising it would require abandoning the liberal commitment to deliberative revisability that organises his prescriptive work. Even a theorist who has documented the depth and stability of semantic structures, who has shown that they operate beneath conscious access and resist voluntary revision, cannot escape the requirement to advise as though agents could simply choose better frames through reflection.

¹⁴ Luntz (2007), *Words That Work: It's Not What You Say, It's What People Hear*. Luntz documents decades of Republican messaging strategy focused on frame activation rather than persuasion.

This is the bind in microcosm. The mechanisms that would work – controlling formation environments, immersive re-socialisation, strategic activation of existing structures – are precisely the ones liberal epistemology must code as ‘manipulation’, ‘propaganda’, or ‘indoctrination’. The mechanisms liberals prefer – education, dialogue, better framing – target a level of agency that cannot reach the relevant constraint. Lakoff’s internal tension is not personal failure. It is the ordinary operation of a framework protecting its constitutive commitments.

Once this is seen, the broader failure of liberal remediation becomes less puzzling. If even the researcher who best documented the semantic constraints cannot consistently recommend strategies that acknowledge them, then the systematic failure of educational interventions, dialogue programs, and deliberative forums is not anomalous. It is the expected outcome when a framework mandates solutions that its own best evidence shows to be structurally inadequate.

Consider the familiar contrast between ‘tax relief’ and ‘tax fairness’. These are not competing labels for a shared, neutral policy domain. They invoke different semantic structures. In the former, taxation is conceptualised as an inherent burden, something imposed and harmful, from which relief is appropriate. In the latter, taxation is framed as a mechanism of distributive justice, a means of sustaining shared goods and rectifying inequality. The difference is not that one group is biased and the other clear-eyed. The difference is that each frame activates a distinct inferential grammar, within which different considerations count as reasons and different conclusions appear compelled.

Within the ‘tax relief’ frame, arguments about fairness or social provision may register as secondary, sentimental, or evasive. Within the ‘tax fairness’ frame, arguments about burden or coercion may register as selfish, regressive, or conceptually confused. These reactions are not post hoc rationalisations layered atop neutral reasoning. They are the immediate outputs of semantic structures that determine what kinds of considerations are even eligible to function as reasons.

Crucially, frame activation operates precognitively. Agents do not typically experience themselves as choosing a frame and then reasoning within it. The frame is already operative at the point where salience is distributed and inferential pathways are opened or foreclosed. This is why appeals to ‘just consider the other side’ so often fail. The other side does not present itself as a coherent alternative set of reasons; it presents itself as missing the point, changing the subject, or reasoning incorrectly.

Seen this way, framing effects do not undermine the account developed in Section III; they corroborate it. They provide empirical evidence that what counts as a reason, what appears relevant, and what feels evidentially compelling are functions of background semantic organisation. The liberal tendency to treat framing as a correctable psychological distortion presupposes precisely what is at issue: that there exists a frame-independent semantic core to which agents can be returned through reflection or education.

There is no such core. Frames are not optional distortions layered atop neutral content. They are constitutive of intelligibility. To ask an agent to ‘set aside the framing’ is not to ask for clearer reasoning; it is to ask them to suspend the very semantic structures that make reasoning possible for them at all.

This reframing of framing effects matters because it shifts the explanatory burden. The persistence of deep disagreement does not require appeal to epistemic vice, motivated reasoning, or cognitive malfunction. It follows from the fact that different semantic frameworks activate different inferential grammars, such that the same policy domain is not merely evaluated differently but structured differently from the outset.

This brings us to a case where the semantic divergence is not speculative or theoretical, but empirically documented at scale. The contrast between attitudes toward ‘Obamacare’ and the ‘Affordable Care Act’ provides precisely such a case: same policy, same referent, systematically divergent responses depending on which frame is activated.

IV.2. The Obamacare / ACA Case

The contrast between public attitudes toward ‘Obamacare’ and the ‘Affordable Care Act’ has become a familiar exhibit in discussions of political cognition. Repeated polling has

shown that respondents who report strong opposition to ‘Obamacare’ often express support for the individual provisions of the Affordable Care Act when those provisions are described without the label.¹⁵ Preventive care mandates, protections for pre-existing conditions, coverage for dependents, and subsidies for low-income patients routinely receive majority approval from respondents who otherwise claim to oppose the policy as a whole.

This pattern is typically interpreted in one of two ways. On a psychological reading, it is treated as evidence of cognitive bias, motivated reasoning, or identity-protective cognition. On a political reading, it is treated as evidence of manipulation, propaganda, or partisan bad faith. Both interpretations miss what is most philosophically instructive about the case.

The phenomenon does not require attributing irrationality, inconsistency, or epistemic malfunction to the agents involved. Nor does it require imputing deceptive intent to political actors. The data can be explained without remainder by the semantic account developed in Section III.

The crucial point is that the two framings do not merely label the same content differently. They activate different semantic structures within the same broader ontological configuration. The referent is held fixed at the level of policy implementation, but the inferential grammar through which that referent is apprehended shifts dramatically.

When the policy is presented under the frame ‘Obamacare’, it activates a semantic field saturated with personalisation, partisanship, and executive authority. The term invokes a particular political figure, a partisan identity, and a narrative of governmental overreach. Within that frame, considerations about coercion, loss of autonomy, bureaucratic expansion, and tribal alignment are rendered salient. Objection is not merely permitted; it is the grammatically appropriate continuation.

¹⁵ For empirical documentation see Tesler (2012), ‘The Spillover of Racialization into Health Care’, *American Journal of Political Science* 56(3): 690-704. The pattern has been replicated across multiple surveys from 2010-2014.

When the same policy is decomposed into its individual provisions and described without the partisan label, a different semantic structure is activated. In that grammar, the salient considerations concern fairness, access to care, protection of the vulnerable, and mitigation of misfortune. Support is not the result of a change of mind; it is the natural output of a different inferential organisation.

Importantly, this is not a case of agents holding contradictory beliefs about a single proposition. It is a case in which the proposition is not individuated as the same proposition across frames. What counts as ‘the policy’ differs depending on which semantic structure is operative. The liberal picture assumes that there is a single content – *the Affordable Care Act* – to which agents adopt inconsistent attitudes. The semantic account shows that this assumption is false. The content itself is grammatically constituted.

This explains why appeals to consistency routinely fail in such cases. From within one frame, support for specific provisions does not register as support for ‘Obamacare’ at all. The inference from ‘I support X’ to ‘I support Obamacare’ is not blocked by bias; it is not licensed by the grammar. Conversely, from within the other frame, opposition to ‘Obamacare’ does not register as opposition to helping the sick or protecting the vulnerable. Those considerations belong to a different semantic organisation.

Seen this way, the polling data are not evidence of epistemic failure. They are evidence of semantic divergence. The agents are responding appropriately to reasons as they are constituted within their operative framework. The failure is not in reasoning but in the liberal assumption that the reasons in question are shared, neutral, and transparently accessible across framings.

This is why the case is philosophically decisive for the present argument. It provides an empirically tractable example in which disagreement persists despite shared exposure to information, shared institutional context, and shared formal referent. What differs is not belief about the facts, but the grammar that determines what counts as a reason, what registers as salient, and what inferential transitions are available.

Accordingly, the Obamacare/ACA case does not support a psychological model on which education, debiasing, or deliberative reflection will restore convergence. Nor does it support a political model on which persuasion fails because of manipulation or moral corruption. It supports a semantic diagnosis: agents are operating within different inferential grammars, and those grammars do not permit the same continuations.

This is precisely the condition under which liberal remedies for indoctrination and closed-mindedness break down. If agents are not failing to see shared reasons, but are instead participating in different semantic structures that constitute different reasons, then appeals to critical thinking, exposure to alternatives, or neutral evaluation cannot do the work they are assigned. The problem is not located at the level of belief revision. It is located at the level of intelligibility itself.

IV.3. Additional Examples: The Systematicity of Semantic Breakdown

The Obamacare/ACA case is not a curiosity, nor a peculiarity of contemporary American politics. It is a particularly clean instance of a general and well-documented phenomenon: the same referent can be apprehended through different semantic structures that organise salience, inference, and evaluation in divergent ways. Once this is recognised, the pattern appears with near-mechanical regularity across domains.

Consider a brief set of familiar examples.¹⁶

Estate Tax vs. Death Tax

The term *estate tax* situates the policy within a semantic structure concerned with wealth transfer, inheritance, and fiscal equity. The relevant inferential moves concern concentration of assets, intergenerational advantage, and public revenue. Within this grammar, taxation appears as a regulatory mechanism applied to accumulated capital.

¹⁶ For systematic evidence of framing effects see Chong & Druckman (2007), 'Framing Theory', *Annual Review of Political Science* 10: 103-126; Entman (1993), 'Framing: Toward Clarification of a Fractured Paradigm', *Journal of Communication* 43(4): 51-58.

By contrast, *death tax* activates a radically different semantic field. The focal point is not wealth but death itself, framed as a moment of personal loss and vulnerability. Taxation appears as a moral violation imposed at a liminal human moment. Objection is grammatically licensed not by economic reasoning but by moral outrage. Again, the divergence is not a matter of misinformation. It is a difference in what the policy is *about*.

Climate Change vs. Climate Crisis

Climate change presents the phenomenon as gradual, technical, and descriptive. The grammar is one of measurement, modelling, and long-term trends. Deliberation is oriented toward uncertainty, trade-offs, and incremental response.

Climate crisis activates a semantic structure of emergency, moral urgency, and impending harm. Within this frame, delay is not prudence but negligence, and disagreement appears as denial rather than scepticism. The shift is not rhetorical decoration; it reorganises what counts as a responsible inference and what counts as an acceptable response.

Illegal Immigrant vs. Undocumented Worker

Illegal immigrant foregrounds illegality as a defining property. The grammar is juridical: law, violation, enforcement, and boundary maintenance. Within this frame, exclusion and punishment are natural continuations.

Undocumented worker foregrounds labour, contribution, and administrative status. The grammar is economic and humanitarian: work, exploitation, precarity. Here, enforcement appears as cruelty or bureaucratic indifference rather than justice. The disagreement is not over the facts of migration, but over which semantic structure governs their interpretation.

Pro-Life vs. Anti-Abortion

Pro-life frames the issue in terms of protection, innocence, and moral obligation. The salient object is life itself, understood as morally prior to competing considerations.

Anti-abortion frames the same position as opposition to a medical procedure, activating considerations of autonomy, bodily integrity, and coercion. Within this grammar,

the same stance appears restrictive rather than protective. Each term pre-sorts the evaluative terrain before any explicit argument begins.

...

In each case, the divergence is not correctable through improved reasoning because reasoning operates within, not on, the activated grammar. Across these cases, the pattern is invariant. The referent remains stable at the level of policy, practice, or social phenomenon. What changes is the semantic structure through which the referent is apprehended. Different framings activate different inferential grammars, different salience structures, and different criteria for what counts as a decisive consideration.

Crucially, these divergences are not the product of conscious choice or reflective endorsement. Frame activation is typically precognitive and non-deliberative. Agents do not first neutrally grasp the content and then decide how to describe it. The description is constitutive of the grasp. What appears to liberal epistemology as distortion or bias is better understood as ordinary semantic functioning.

This generality matters. It shows that the Obamacare case is not an isolated failure of reasoning, nor a contingent artefact of polarisation. It is a systematic feature of how meaning operates within linguistic practices. Where semantic structures diverge, shared access to reasons dissolves – not because agents are irrational or uncooperative, but because the conditions under which something can count as a reason are not shared.

Once this is seen, the liberal strategy of diagnosing indoctrination by appeal to neutral framing, shared evidence, or improved deliberation loses its footing. The problem is not that agents are trapped in bad frames that could be escaped through reflection. It is that framing is not an optional overlay on an otherwise neutral semantic core. It is the mechanism by which that core is constituted in the first place.

The upshot is stark but unavoidable. If these cases are representative – and there is no reason to think they are not – then the failure of convergence under deliberation is not anomalous. It is the expected outcome when semantic grammars diverge. And any

epistemology that presupposes otherwise has misunderstood the terrain on which it is operating.

IV.4. What This Shows

The preceding cases invite a familiar set of misdiagnoses. It is important to be explicit about what they do *not* show.

They do not show that:

- agents are irrational,
- agents are insufficiently reflective or critical,
- agents are failing to attend to available evidence,
- agents are indoctrinated in Ranalli's sense of having their epistemic capacities foreclosed by defective education.

Nothing in the framing evidence licenses these conclusions. In each case, agents display stable, internally coherent patterns of response. Their judgments are intelligible, systematic, and responsive to what, from within their semantic location, count as reasons. The problem is not a breakdown of reasoning. It is a breakdown of *shared semantic footing*.

What the evidence does show is structurally different.

First, responses are determined by which semantic frame is activated. Framing does not merely colour an already-grasped content; it constitutes what the content is taken to be about. Different frames activate different inferential grammars, different salience structures, and different evaluative pathways. Once a frame is active, certain considerations present themselves as obvious, others as marginal, and still others as irrelevant or unintelligible.

Second, frame activation occurs beneath conscious access. Agents do not typically experience themselves as selecting a frame and then reasoning within it. The frame is already operative by the time deliberation begins. This is why post hoc reflection so often takes the form of rationalisation rather than revision: the grammar that determines what will count as a reason is already in place.

Third, frame activation is not subject to voluntary control through deliberation. One cannot simply decide, by reflecting harder or being more open-minded, which semantic

structure will govern one's uptake of a term or policy. Deliberation presupposes a frame; it does not choose one. The liberal injunction to 'step back and consider the issue neutrally' misfires because neutrality is not an available stance. There is no deliberative switch that toggles between grammars.

Finally, agency operates downstream of semantic activation. Once a frame is active, agents exercise agency in perfectly ordinary ways: weighing considerations, drawing inferences, endorsing conclusions, acting on reasons. But this agency is *thin*. It concerns execution within a space of intelligibility whose contours the agent did not author and cannot revise through the very deliberative capacities it enables.

Seen in this light, the framing evidence is not a psychological curiosity. It is the empirical surface of the semantic constraints developed in Section III. What looks like disagreement about policies is often disagreement about what counts as a reason, what kind of thing is under discussion, and what standards of evaluation are even in play. Those disagreements are not resolved by better reasoning because they are not *failures* of reasoning.

This is what framework-relativity looks like in practice. Not chaos. Not relativistic anything-goes. Just agents competently reasoning within different grammars that do not align. And once that is acknowledged, the liberal hope that indoctrination can be diagnosed and remedied through agent-level epistemic correction begins to look less like optimism and more like a category mistake with good manners.

IV.5. Implications for Ranalli's Diagnosis

Once the framing evidence is taken seriously, the limits of Ranalli's diagnostic framework come into sharp focus.¹⁷ The problem is not that his criteria are vaguely formulated or poorly motivated. It is that they are aimed at the wrong level of constraint.

¹⁷ Some liberal theorists have attempted to incorporate Wittgensteinian or pragmatist insights (Rorty 1989; certain readings of late Rawls). Whether such frameworks escape the

If agents' responses vary systematically with framing despite unchanged facts and identical referents, then the relevant failure cannot be located at the level of *responding to reasons*. The agents are not overlooking available considerations, suppressing counterevidence, or failing to engage in critical reflection. They are responding exactly as one would expect given the semantic structures through which those considerations are rendered intelligible.

The constraint, therefore, is not downstream of reasoning. It is upstream of it. It operates at the level of what *registers* as a reason in the first place.

This point directly undermines the core of Ranalli's diagnosis. His account presupposes that indoctrination can be identified by features such as the suppression of critical thinking, resistance to counterevidence, or foreclosure of alternatives. But the framing evidence shows that these markers systematically misfire in cases of deep disagreement. What appears, from within one framework, as resistance to evidence often looks, from within another, like principled selectivity. What appears as foreclosure of alternatives often reflects the fact that those 'alternatives' do not show up as candidates for consideration at all.

Crucially, this is not because the agent is epistemically defective. The agent *is* thinking critically – within the inferential grammar activated by the frame. The agent *is* responding to evidence – as their framework determines what counts as evidence, what weight it carries, and what conclusions it supports. The agent is not refusing to deliberate; they are deliberating competently within a semantic space that the evaluator does not share.

Ranalli's criteria therefore diagnose pathology where there is none. They treat framework-relative intelligibility as epistemic vice. The mistake is structural rather than

constraints identified here is a separate question. The critique targets liberal epistemology as it typically operates in contemporary analytic philosophy, where semantic accessibility is treated as unproblematic.

moral. By assuming shared access to reasons, neutral diagnostic criteria, and deliberative revisability of framework-constitutive commitments, the account mislocates the source of constraint at the level of individual epistemic agency. The framing evidence shows that this level is too shallow to do the explanatory work required. The relevant constraint operates not at the level of belief-revision within a framework, but at the level of framework-constitution itself – a level that deliberation presupposes rather than accesses.

What looks like indoctrination, on Ranalli's model, is often nothing more than the ordinary operation of a semantic framework doing exactly what frameworks do: organising salience, shaping inference, and determining what can count as a reason at all. Once that is acknowledged, the aspiration to diagnose indoctrination through agent-level epistemic correction no longer appears merely difficult. It appears conceptually incoherent.

This does not yet tell us what *would* work. It tells us something more basic and more unsettling: why the standard remedies cannot.

V. Locating Agency Correctly

„Man kann tun, was er will, aber er kann in jedem gegebenen Augenblick seines Lebens nur ein Bestimmtes wollen und schlechterdings nichts anderes als dieses eine‘.

– Arthur Schopenhauer, *Über die Freiheit des menschlichen Willens* (1839)

Translation: ‘One can choose what to do, but not what to want’.

The grammatical constraint explains why deliberative agency cannot be the primary causal mechanism of framework revision; the variance claim explains why, empirically, it contributes negligible explanatory power even when present.

Contemporary political psychology (Haidt, Kahan, Taber & Lodge) documents systematic divergence in political reasoning. This work typically interprets such divergence in terms of cognitive bias, motivated reasoning, or differential moral intuitions – that is, as agent-level processing failures. The present account locates constraint upstream: not in how agents process information, but in what can count as information within their semantic

frameworks. Psychological explanations are not wrong but incomplete. They describe surface regularities without accessing the grammatical structure that produces them.

V.1. Dennett's Thin Compatibilism

Any serious account of indoctrination, responsibility, or deliberation must begin by resisting a familiar temptation: the temptation to make agency either omnipotent or illusory. The argument developed so far does neither. It does not deny that agents deliberate, choose, and act, nor does it reduce human behaviour to mechanical reflex or epiphenomenal noise. What it does deny is that agency operates at every level liberal epistemology routinely assigns to it.

Schopenhauer's famous dictum – that we can do what we will but cannot will what we will – captures precisely the distinction at stake here. Liberal epistemology focuses on the first capacity: agents can deliberate, weigh considerations, and choose among options (thin agency). But it tacitly assumes the second capacity as well: that agents can, through reflection, revise the background conditions that determine what even appears as an option worth choosing (robust agency). The former is real. The latter is the grammatical error. We deliberate within frameworks; we do not deliberate our way into them.

A useful starting point here is Daniel Dennett's compatibilist account of free will (Dennett 1984; 2003). Dennett's project, at least in its modest and defensible form, is not to rescue a metaphysically extravagant notion of freedom, but to show that agency worth wanting survives once we abandon contra-causal fantasies. On this view, agents are free insofar as they can consider reasons, weigh alternatives, anticipate consequences, and act in ways that are responsive to those considerations. This kind of agency is perfectly compatible with causal determination, psychological constraint, and environmental influence.

Dennett's familiar examples are deliberately mundane. Choosing what colour shirt to wear in the morning, deciding what to order from a menu, opting to take one route rather than another – these are paradigmatic cases of agency in action (Dennett 1984, ch. 2). The agent surveys a small space of available options, considers preferences and situational constraints, and selects one. Nothing about this process requires metaphysical

indeterminism or authorship of one's own character *ex nihilo*. And nothing about it is illusory. The choice is real, the deliberation is genuine, and the outcome is causally efficacious.

This thin compatibilist notion of agency is not a concession made grudgingly for argumentative convenience. It is exactly right for most contexts of ordinary life. It captures what we ordinarily mean when we hold people responsible for everyday actions, praise them for prudence, or criticise them for carelessness. It explains why advice, incentives, and local reasoning often work perfectly well within shared practices. When the grammar is shared, agency matters.

What this account pointedly does *not* require is that agents be the authors of the evaluative frameworks within which such deliberation takes place. Dennett's compatibilism does not claim that agents choose the criteria by which reasons count as reasons, or that they can, through reflection alone, revise the background grammar that determines what even shows up as an option. The agent chooses *within* a space of intelligibility; they do not generate that space from scratch.

This distinction is easy to miss because Dennett himself often emphasises how much agency survives once we abandon metaphysical excess. But survival is not sovereignty. Thin compatibilism secures execution-level agency: the capacity to select among available options given one's preferences, beliefs, and situational constraints. It does not secure authorship-level agency: the capacity to step outside the semantic and normative structures that determine what counts as a reason, what appears salient, and what feels like a live alternative in the first place.

That limitation is not a defect in Dennett's account. It is one of its virtues. Compatibilism is attractive precisely because it refuses to saddle agency with impossible burdens. The trouble begins only when this modest, defensible notion of agency is quietly pressed into service to do work it was never designed to do – work that requires agents to revise the very conditions under which reasons become intelligible to them at all.

For the purposes of this paper, then, Dennett's thin compatibilism sets the baseline. Agency exists. It is real. It matters. But its scope is limited. And once we are clear about where it operates successfully, we can begin to see where liberal epistemology systematically asks it to operate where it cannot.

The next step is to make that boundary explicit.

V.2. But Thin Agency Cannot Do Robust Work

Once thin compatibilist agency is on the table, the crucial question is no longer whether agents can choose, but what kind of choosing is being asked of them. This is where liberal epistemology, Ranalli included, quietly overreaches.

Thin agency is the capacity to choose *within* a set of given parameters. It operates against a background of already-formed preferences, salience structures, inferential habits, and evaluative standards. The agent deliberates, weighs considerations, and selects among options that present themselves as intelligible and live. This is real agency, but it is bounded. It presupposes a space of reasons rather than generating one.

Robust agency, by contrast, would involve authorship of the parameters themselves. It would require agents not merely to select among available reasons, but to revise the standards by which something counts as a reason at all. It would require stepping back from the grammar that structures deliberation and evaluating that grammar using criteria that are not already supplied by it. This is not just a quantitative expansion of thin agency; it is a qualitative shift to a different level of operation altogether.

Ranalli's account of indoctrination requires this stronger notion. His diagnosis presupposes that agents can recognise when their epistemic environment is distorting, step back from the commitments that structure their reasoning, and deliberately revise those commitments in light of reasons that remain available despite the distortion. Indoctrination, on his view, is objectionable precisely because it interferes with this capacity for reflective self-correction. Remediation, correspondingly, consists in restoring it through critical thinking, openness, and exposure to alternatives.

But this remediation story only works if agents possess robust agency. They must be able to evaluate not just beliefs *within* a framework, but the framework itself. They must be able to treat their own criteria of relevance, evidential sufficiency, and inferential legitimacy as objects of deliberation rather than as the background conditions that make deliberation possible. In short, they must be able to do precisely what the philosophy of language in Section III shows they cannot do.

Thin agency cannot deliver this. An agent operating with thin agency can deliberate impeccably whilst remaining entirely unable to question the semantic structures that determine what counts as deliberation-worthy in the first place.¹⁸ They can reason well, argue coherently, respond to evidence, and revise beliefs – all without ever encountering their framework as something optional or revisable. From within a framework, its grammar does not present itself as one choice among others. It presents itself as the way reasoning works.

This is why the appeal to ‘choosing openness’ or ‘deciding to be receptive to counterevidence’ does not bridge the gap. Openness itself is a norm whose content is framework-relative. What counts as being open-minded in one semantic grammar may register as gullibility, moral abdication, or category confusion in another. Asking an agent to adopt openness as a corrective presupposes that openness is already recognisable as a virtue within their inferential ecology. That is exactly what is at issue.

The distinction, then, is not between agency and no agency, but between execution and authorship. Thin agency governs execution: selecting among options rendered

¹⁸ Frankfurt (1971) distinguishes between first-order desires (wanting X) and second-order desires (wanting to want X). The present distinction between thin and robust agency is structurally parallel but operates at the level of semantic frameworks rather than individual desires. Frankfurt, H.G. (1971), ‘Freedom of the Will and the Concept of a Person’, *Journal of Philosophy* 68(1): 5-20.

intelligible by one's semantic environment. Robust agency would require authorship: the capacity to redesign that environment from within. Liberal epistemology routinely slides from the former to the latter without noticing the shift, treating everyday deliberative competence as evidence of a much deeper self-authoring capacity.

This slide is not an innocent mistake. It is structurally motivated. Without robust agency, liberal diagnoses of indoctrination lose their footing. If agents cannot revise the conditions of intelligibility through deliberation, then indoctrination cannot be identified as a failure of rational responsiveness, nor remedied by educational or dialogical means that presuppose precisely that capacity.

What thin compatibilism gives us is agency that works locally and reliably *once a grammar is in place*. What Ranalli needs is agency that can rewrite the grammar itself. The former exists. The latter is a philosophical fiction – one that becomes increasingly untenable once semantic constraints are taken seriously.

The next question, then, is not whether agency survives, but where it survives, and where it does not. And that question forces a reassessment of what responsibility, blame, and remediation can coherently mean in cases of deep framework divergence.

V.3. Agency as Rounding Error

The claim emerging from the preceding sections is not that agency disappears, nor that deliberation is an illusion. It is that the explanatory power of agency is radically scale-sensitive. In some domains it matters a great deal. In others, it is technically present but explanatorily negligible. The most accurate way to capture this is statistical rather than metaphysical.

In statistics, a *rounding error* is not zero. It exists. It is measurable. But relative to the dominant variables, it explains so little variance that treating it as causally decisive would be misleading. This is the status agency occupies in cases of deep semantic divergence.

Within a shared ontological framework, agency explains substantial variance. Differences in attentiveness, intellectual honesty, cognitive skill, and effort matter. Thoughtful reasoning produces different outcomes than sloppy reasoning. Exposure to

evidence, correction of error, and reflective deliberation can and often do shift beliefs. In these contexts, liberal epistemology works tolerably well because the semantic ground is already shared. The grammar is in place. Agency operates where it is supposed to.

Across divergent frameworks, however, agency explains almost nothing of interest. The dominant explanatory variables are semantic and ontological: which inferential grammar is operative, which salience structures are activated, which criteria of reasonableness are in play. Against these factors, individual-level deliberation contributes negligible variance. The agent may deliberate carefully or carelessly, sincerely or strategically, but the outcome will overwhelmingly be shaped by the framework within which deliberation occurs.

This is not eliminativism about agency. It is a claim about where agency does explanatory work. To insist that agency must explain cross-framework disagreement because it explains intra-framework disagreement is a category error. It is like insisting that personal driving skill must explain tectonic plate movement because it explains traffic accidents. The level of analysis is wrong.

Seen this way, many familiar liberal pathologies become intelligible. Educational interventions fail not because participants refuse to think, but because thinking harder does not alter the semantic parameters that determine what thinking *is about*. Dialogue stalls not because agents are obstinate, but because the reasons offered do not register as reasons within the relevant grammar. Appeals to autonomy misfire because autonomy, as thin agency, operates downstream of the constraints being appealed to.

The rounding error formulation also explains why these failures are so often misdiagnosed as moral or epistemic defects. When agency is assumed to be the dominant variable, any failure of convergence must be attributed to bad faith, closed-mindedness, or irrationality. But once semantic structure is recognised as the dominant variable, those diagnoses lose traction. The agent is doing exactly what agency allows them to do: reasoning competently within the only space of reasons available to them.

This reframing sharpens rather than softens the critique. Liberal epistemology does not merely overestimate the moral capacities of agents. It misallocates explanatory weight. It treats a residual variable as decisive and a dominant variable as background noise. The result is a systematic misunderstanding of why disagreement persists and why remediation so reliably fails.

Agency matters. But it matters locally, not globally. It shapes outcomes once a framework is in place; it does not author the framework itself. To expect it to do so is not optimism. It is a modelling error.

And once that error is corrected, the next conclusion follows with uncomfortable clarity: if agency is a rounding error at the level where indoctrination is supposed to operate, then diagnoses and remedies pitched at the level of agency cannot possibly reach the phenomenon they claim to address.

V.4. The Variance Model

At this point the dispute can be stated with enough precision to stop it drifting into moralising or metaphysics. The disagreement between liberal epistemology and the present account is not about whether agency exists, but about how much explanatory work it does, and at what level. One way to make this explicit is to model belief-formation outcomes in terms of variance attribution.

Consider the following schematic model:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Outcome} = & \beta_1(\text{Semantic Framework}) + \beta_2(\text{Frame Activation}) + \beta_3(\text{Formation History}) \\ & + \beta_4(\text{Agency}) + \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

The coefficients here are not offered as empirically measured constants.¹⁹ They are illustrative weightings, intended to capture relative explanatory contribution rather than exact magnitudes. Their value lies in forcing clarity about what is doing the causal work.

¹⁹ The variance model borrows notation from statistical regression but is not offered as an empirical measurement. It is a heuristic for clarifying relative explanatory contributions.

Within-Framework Contexts

When agents share a semantic framework – roughly, when they agree on what counts as a reason, what counts as evidence, and what inferential moves are licensed – agency explains a substantial portion of variance.

In such contexts:

- $\beta_4 \approx 0.3-0.4$

Differences in attentiveness, intellectual discipline, openness to counterevidence, and reasoning skill matter. Two agents exposed to the same information can arrive at different conclusions because one reasons carefully and the other sloppily. Educational interventions, critical thinking instruction, and deliberative exchange often succeed here precisely because the semantic grammar is already shared. Liberal epistemology performs best in this regime, which is why it mistakes this success for generality.

Cross-Framework Contexts

When agents operate within divergent ontological frameworks, the picture changes dramatically. Here, the dominant sources of variance lie upstream of deliberation.

In such contexts:

- β_1 (Semantic framework): dominant
- β_2 (Frame activation): substantial
- β_3 (Formation history): moderate
- β_4 (Agency): negligible

The precise values are not the point. The order of magnitude is. Semantic structure and frame activation explain nearly all of the variance. Agency remains non-zero, but its contribution is so small relative to the dominant terms that treating it as decisive is analytically irresponsible.

For formal treatment of effect sizes in social science see Cohen (1988), *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences*.

This is what it means to say that agency functions as a *rounding error* in cross-framework disagreement. The agent deliberates, reasons, weighs considerations, and reaches conclusions – but the space in which that activity occurs has already been structured in ways the agent cannot access or revise through deliberation itself.

Why This Matters

This variance model makes explicit what liberal epistemology leaves tacit. When Ranalli attributes epistemic failure to deficiencies in agency – closed-mindedness, resistance to reasons, failure of autonomy – he is implicitly assigning a high β_4 across all contexts. The empirical and semantic evidence shows that this assignment is wildly inaccurate in precisely the cases that motivate concern about indoctrination.

The model also explains why liberal remedies feel intuitively compelling yet consistently underperform. They target the smallest coefficient whilst leaving the dominant variables untouched. This is not a failure of execution. It is a failure of causal diagnosis.

Once the variance is allocated correctly, the structure of the problem shifts. Indoctrination, where it exists, cannot be primarily an agent-level pathology. It must be located in the formation and stabilisation of semantic frameworks themselves – processes that liberal epistemology is structurally committed to treating as off-limits.

And that, unfortunately for liberal theories of remediation, is not a bug. It is the design specification.

V.5. Why Remediation Fails

This section draws out the practical consequence of the variance allocation just established. Once the variance is allocated correctly, the persistent failure of liberal remediation ceases to be puzzling. It becomes inevitable.

Ranalli's proposed interventions – critical thinking instruction, epistemic virtue cultivation, exposure to alternatives, reflective openness – are all designed to operate on a single variable: agency, understood as conscious deliberative capacity. In the terms of the variance model, they are interventions aimed squarely at β_4 .

This would be sensible if β_4 carried substantial explanatory weight in the cases under discussion. It does not.

In cross-framework contexts – the very contexts that motivate concern about indoctrination – β_4 is vanishingly small. The dominant contributors to belief-formation are semantic framework (β_1) and frame activation (β_2), both of which operate upstream of deliberation and beneath conscious access. No amount of refinement at the level of deliberative execution can compensate for mislocating the source of constraint.

The result is a familiar pattern: earnest, well-funded, carefully designed interventions that reliably fail to produce durable change. This failure is routinely misinterpreted as evidence of stubbornness, bad faith, moral vice, or deeper indoctrination. In fact, it is evidence of something far more mundane. The intervention is aimed at the wrong variable.

An analogy may help, if only to underline the scale of the mismatch. Attempting to remediate cross-framework disagreement by improving deliberative agency is like attempting to predict election outcomes by measuring shoe size. Shoe size may exhibit some technical correlation with voting behaviour in certain populations. It is not noise. But it explains essentially none of the variance that matters. Refining the measurement will not improve predictive power. The problem is not insufficient precision; it is conceptual mislocation.

The same is true here. Liberal epistemology insists on treating indoctrination as a defect in how agents reason – how they weigh evidence, respond to counterarguments, or exercise autonomy. But the empirical and semantic evidence shows that, in deep disagreement, agents are already reasoning competently within the inferential grammar their framework supplies. What differs is not the quality of reasoning but the grammar in which reasoning occurs.

This explains a further, often overlooked feature of remediation failure: interventions frequently produce momentary compliance rather than genuine revision. Participants learn to parrot alternative framings, acknowledge counterarguments, or perform epistemic virtues in controlled settings. But once the intervention context dissolves, prior patterns reassert

themselves. The semantic framework has not shifted; only surface-level behaviour has been temporarily modulated. Liberal epistemology mistakes this for progress because it measures success at the level it knows how to see.

Crucially, none of this requires denying agency or rationality. Agents deliberate. They respond to reasons. They exhibit consistency, sensitivity to evidence, and inferential discipline. What they do not do – and what they cannot be expected to do – is author the semantic conditions that determine what will count as a reason in the first place. Asking them to do so is not empowering. It is incoherent.

This is why Ranalli's diagnosis fails even on its own terms. His criteria for indoctrination – resistance to counterevidence, foreclosure of alternatives, suppression of critical reflection – are all assessed from within a semantic framework that already determines what counts as evidence, what counts as an alternative, and what counts as reflection rather than derailment. When those criteria are applied across frameworks, they do not diagnose epistemic malfunction. They merely register semantic misalignment.

The remediation fails because it must fail. Liberal epistemology is committed, at a structural level, to solutions that operate through agent-level deliberation whilst refusing to countenance the kinds of formative, environmental, and re-socialising mechanisms that would be required to shift semantic frameworks themselves. Those mechanisms exist. They are well understood. And they are precisely the ones liberal theory is normatively bound to condemn as illegitimate.

The result is a theory that explains failure as pathology, prescribes remedies that cannot reach the constraint, and then expresses surprise when the problem persists. Once agency is located correctly – as real but limited, effective within frameworks but negligible across them – that pattern stops looking like bad luck and starts looking like design.

What liberal epistemology cannot admit is that its preferred remedies fail not because they are insufficiently applied, but because they target a variable that, in the relevant cases, does not do the causal work.

V.6. What Would Work (and Why It's Foreclosed)

To prescribe which mechanisms 'should' be used would require precisely the framework-transcendent standpoint this paper argues is unavailable. The point is not that certain mechanisms are better or worse, but that liberal epistemology systematically mistargets constraint by privileging mechanisms (education, dialogue) that operate where they explain negligible variance.

Once the variance is correctly allocated, an awkward fact becomes unavoidable. The mechanisms that *do* explain meaningful variation in belief and judgment are neither mysterious nor undiscovered. They are well known, empirically tractable, and routinely deployed. They are simply unavailable to liberal epistemology as legitimate tools.

Start with β_2 : frame activation. Unlike deep framework formation, frame activation is both causally substantial and manipulable in real time. Strategic framing can reliably shift salience, reorganise inferential pathways, and alter what registers as a reason without changing underlying policy content or factual inputs. This is not speculative. It is the everyday working knowledge of political consultants, advertisers, campaign strategists, and communications professionals.

Frank Luntz did not succeed because he uncovered a secret about human irrationality. He succeeded because he respected the semantic constraint. He tested which terms activated existing inferential grammars and then disciplined messaging to trigger them consistently. No attempt was made to persuade across frameworks or to revise fundamental commitments. The work was done upstream of deliberation, where the leverage actually is.

Liberal epistemology, however, cannot endorse this strategy without self-contradiction. Strategic frame activation must be redescribed as *manipulation*, *spin*, or *propaganda*, because acknowledging its legitimacy would require conceding that belief revision is not primarily a deliberative achievement. The very mechanism that works must be normatively disqualified in advance.

Now consider β_1 : deep framework formation. Here the effects are even larger and even more durable. Long-term immersion in linguistic practices, institutional environments, and normative expectations shapes what becomes intelligible at all. This is how semantic frameworks are formed, stabilised, and reproduced across generations. Again, none of this is controversial as a sociological or historical claim.

What is foreclosed is acknowledging it as a site of legitimate intervention. Any mechanism capable of reshaping β_1 must operate through formative environments rather than episodic persuasion. And such mechanisms – unsurprisingly – are precisely the ones liberal epistemology is structurally committed to condemning. They are redescribed as coercive, illegitimate, or morally toxic long before their causal efficacy can be acknowledged.

The bind is therefore not accidental. It is structural.

- Mechanisms that could shift outcomes meaningfully operate at levels liberal theory refuses to touch.
- Mechanisms liberal theory permits operate at levels that explain negligible variance in the relevant cases.

This is why the failure of remediation is so stable across domains. It is not that the wrong people are implementing the right ideas. It is that the ideas are designed to avoid the only mechanisms that could succeed.

Importantly, none of this requires endorsing the forbidden mechanisms. The point is diagnostic, not prescriptive. The argument is not ‘therefore we should manipulate, indoctrinate, or re-engineer belief’. The argument is that a theory that both condemns the effective mechanisms and insists on ineffective ones has no explanatory right to be surprised by its own failure.

Liberal epistemology wants belief change without leverage, revision without formation, persuasion without asymmetry. It wants agency to do work that agency, by its own constraints, cannot do. And it wants to treat the resulting persistence of disagreement as evidence of individual pathology rather than structural mislocation.

Once this is seen, the problem of indoctrination looks very different. The question is no longer why some agents fail to respond to reasons they ‘have access to’. Rather, one must ask why liberal theory insists on modelling belief change as something that must occur at precisely the level where it is least causally effective.

That is not a moral failing. It is a grammatical one.

VI. Implications

VI.1. For Indoctrination Theory

The account developed here explains not only Ranalli’s specific diagnostic failure but a broader and highly persistent pattern of mutual unintelligibility. When ontological frameworks diverge – whether between analytic and continental philosophy, progressive and conservative politics, or secular and religious worldviews – the same structure reliably appears. Agents operating competently within different grammars mistake semantic misalignment for epistemic vice. What presents itself as closed-mindedness, irrationality, or indoctrination is, on this account, the predictable result of agents reasoning fluently within incompatible backgrounds of intelligibility.

The persistence of these divides, despite centuries of dialogue, education, and institutionalised deliberation, is therefore not evidence of widespread cognitive or moral failure. It is evidence of constraint operating at a level deliberative remediation cannot reach. This explanatory breadth is not scope creep; it is confirmation that the diagnosis is structural rather than local.

The critique can be restated in technical terms. Liberal epistemology applies a well-behaved deliberative function – rational evaluation, epistemic virtue cultivation, corrective dialogue – to a semantic input space it has never properly specified. The assumed inputs (shared access to reasons, neutral diagnostic criteria, deliberative revisability of frameworks)

are malformed relative to the actual structure of meaning-use. The resulting pathologies are not failures of rational agents but artefacts of a type error at the level of semantics.²⁰

Within shared frameworks, where semantic inputs approximate the model's implicit specification, the function produces sensible results. Agents disagree, revise beliefs, improve reasoning, and sometimes converge. This partial success explains the durability of the liberal model. It works often enough that its domain restrictions remain invisible. But once inputs shift from intra-framework variance to cross-framework divergence, the same function becomes noise-amplifying. It misclassifies semantic difference as epistemic vice, competence as pathology, and framework-relative consistency as indoctrination. The failure is upstream of rationality, not downstream of it – a specification error mistaken for an implementation failure.

Once this is recognised, the education–indoctrination distinction central to Ranalli's project collapses. Both education and indoctrination operate at the level of semantic formation. Both shape the background practices that determine what will later count as a reason, what will register as evidence, which explanations will feel natural, and which objections will seem decisive. The difference between them is not structural but normative. We code as *education* those forms of ontological formation whose outcomes we approve, and as *indoctrination* those whose outcomes we reject.

The diagnostic metaphor is semantic impact: the moment of framework boundary-crossing where concept structure either preserves or breaks. 'Nihilism' survives intact within naturalist frameworks (thin descriptor). It does not survive impact into theistic frameworks

²⁰ The type error diagnosis follows a pattern familiar in philosophy of science: applying well-formed operations to ill-specified domains produces artifacts rather than discoveries. Compare Kuhn's account of paradigm incommensurability or Feyerabend's critique of methodological universalism (Feyerabend 1975, *Against Method*).

(reconstituted as thick negation). This is not translation failure in the sense of needing better words. It is grammatical incompatibility at the level of what-kind-of-thing-a-concept-can-be.

This is not a cynical claim about bad faith. It is a claim about mechanism. There are no neutral criteria by which to distinguish education from indoctrination without presupposing the very framework under dispute. Any proposed diagnostic standard – openness to counterevidence, encouragement of critical thinking, responsiveness to reasons – already embeds substantive semantic commitments about what counts as evidence, what qualifies as criticism, and which reasons deserve uptake. To apply such standards across frameworks is not to diagnose a failure; it is to enforce one grammar whilst mistaking it for a tribunal.

Bernard Williams' distinction between thick and thin ethical concepts clarifies what is happening.²¹ Liberal epistemology treats 'reason', 'evidence', 'openness', and 'epistemic responsibility' as thin concepts – abstractable, framework-transcendent, universally applicable. But these are actually thick concepts whose application conditions, inferential roles, and normative force are framework-relative. When Ranalli diagnoses 'failure to respond to reasons', he is wielding a thick concept that does not survive transfer across frameworks. The target framework cannot house it. What liberal epistemology calls epistemic vice is thick concept non-transferability misrecognised as moral failure.

What liberal epistemology diagnoses as epistemic vice – closed-mindedness, resistance to reasons, failure of intellectual virtue - is often nothing more than thick concept

²¹ Bernard Williams, *Ethics and the Limits of Philosophy* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1985), ch. 8. Williams distinguishes thick concepts (e.g., *courageous*, *brutal*) from thin ones (e.g., *good*, *ought*). Thick concepts are simultaneously world-guided and action-guiding; their descriptive and evaluative components are fused and resist separation. Crucially, they do not transfer across incommensurable frameworks without loss of their practical and inferential roles.

non-transferability mistaken for moral failure. The agent is not refusing to respond appropriately within their framework. The concept is refusing to survive impact.

The implication for indoctrination theory is therefore stark. A framework that presupposes shared semantic accessibility cannot diagnose cases where that accessibility is precisely what is missing. Ranalli's criteria do not fail because they are insufficiently refined, but because they are addressed to the wrong level of description. They assume the problem lies in how agents reason, when the constraint lies in what can appear to them as a reason at all.

That is the limit case for liberal epistemology. And it is not an embarrassment at the margins. It is the predictable consequence of treating semantic formation as if it were merely epistemic error, and of mistaking ontological divergence for remediable deliberative failure.

VI.2. For Epistemic Responsibility

If the preceding analysis is correct, then a familiar practice in liberal epistemology becomes untenable: holding agents epistemically responsible for failing to respond to reasons that are recognisable as reasons only within semantic frameworks they do not inhabit. The problem is not that such agents refuse to deliberate, reason poorly, or lack agency. It is that the deliberative space within which agency operates is already structured by background grammars that determine what can register as a reason in the first place.

This point is easily misunderstood, so it bears emphasis. The argument does not deny epistemic responsibility as such. It denies a *particular localisation* of responsibility. Liberal epistemology tends to locate responsibility at the level of momentary deliberative acts: did the agent consider the evidence, weigh the reasons, remain open to revision? But if reasons are framework-relative role-occupants rather than neutral objects in a shared epistemic space, then failure to uptake them cannot be straightforwardly attributed to a lapse of epistemic virtue.

Agents can be fully competent deliberators within their semantic frameworks and yet systematically fail to recognise what others take to be decisive reasons. In such cases, blaming the agent for epistemic failure misidentifies the site of constraint. The failure is not

volitional, nor is it corrigible through exhortations to think harder, be more open-minded, or engage in better dialogue. Agency here is real, but it is operating within parameters it did not author and cannot simply step outside.

This forces a relocation of epistemic responsibility rather than its elimination. Responsibility may plausibly attach to formation conditions: the diachronic processes by which agents are inducted into particular semantic practices; the educational, familial, religious, and media environments that stabilise inferential grammars long before reflective agency is in play. It may also attach to institutional structures that reward, amplify, or entrench certain semantic frameworks whilst marginalising others, thereby shaping what can later appear as common sense or extremism.

What cannot be sustained is the idea that epistemic responsibility primarily attaches to isolated moments of deliberation abstracted from these conditions. Holding an agent responsible for failing to respond to a reason they cannot recognise as a reason is akin to holding them responsible for failing to hear a frequency outside the range of their auditory system. The metaphor is imperfect, but the structural point is clear: responsibility cannot outrun intelligibility.

This does not entail that ‘anything goes’, nor does it license epistemic quietism. It entails that responsibility must be indexed to the level at which genuine control and variation exist. Within shared semantic frameworks, epistemic responsibility remains robust. Sloppy reasoning, motivated inference, selective evidence uptake, and intellectual laziness are real phenomena, and agents can rightly be held accountable for them. But across framework boundaries, where semantic access itself diverges, responsibility cannot be coherently assigned to the deliberative act without committing the very grammatical error this paper diagnoses.

The upshot is uncomfortable but precise. Liberal epistemology overextends a legitimate notion of epistemic responsibility beyond the domain in which it can sensibly apply. In doing so, it converts structural semantic constraints into individual moral failings.

What presents itself as a demand for accountability is, in these cases, a category mistake – one that mistakes the limits of intelligibility for defects of character.

VI.3. For Deliberative Political Philosophy

If the argument advanced in this paper is correct, its implications extend beyond theories of indoctrination to deliberative political philosophy more generally. Any account that treats political deliberation as operating over shared semantic materials – shared reasons, common evaluative standards, mutually recognisable justificatory moves – presupposes precisely the kind of semantic accessibility that the foregoing analysis denies.²²

Canonical deliberative models, from Rawlsian public reason to Habermasian ideal speech situations, are built on the assumption that political disagreement takes place against a background of shared intelligibility (Rawls 1993; Habermas 1996). Citizens may disagree about values, priorities, or empirical assessments, but the reasons offered in justification are assumed to be recognisable as reasons by all properly functioning participants. Deliberation, on these views, is meant to filter preferences through publicly accessible standards of justification, yielding legitimacy through reason-giving rather than mere aggregation or force.²³

²² For representative deliberative democratic accounts see also Gutmann & Thompson (1996), *Democracy and Disagreement*; Cohen (1989), 'Deliberation and Democratic Legitimacy'.

²³ Rawls' 'overlapping consensus' (*Political Liberalism*, 1993) proposes that citizens can agree on political principles despite incommensurable comprehensive doctrines – e.g., a Catholic, secular liberal, and utilitarian all supporting religious freedom for different reasons. But this treats semantic alignment as sufficient for consensus. If frameworks determine not just *why* but *what* 'religious freedom' means – its inferential role, its scope, its implications – then apparent agreement may be accidental convergence on a policy label rather than shared reasoning. Like stopped clocks all showing 3:15 at 3:15, the alignment is

The diagnosis developed here puts pressure on that assumption at its foundation. If what counts as a reason, what registers as evidence, and what appears salient are all framework-relative – embedded in semantic grammars that are not themselves objects of neutral deliberation – then deliberation cannot perform the work these theories assign to it. The problem is not that deliberative ideals are insufficiently realised in practice. It is that the very conditions required for their operation are unavailable in cases of deep framework divergence.

This does not show that deliberative political philosophy is incoherent tout court, nor that deliberation plays no role in political life. It shows that its scope is narrower than its proponents typically acknowledge. Within shared frameworks, deliberation can be genuinely productive – refining positions, exposing contradictions, and enabling convergence. The problem arises when deliberative models are extended to cases of deep framework divergence, where the very conditions for their operation are absent. Where semantic frameworks are sufficiently shared, deliberation can refine positions, expose inconsistencies, and discipline reasoning. Where they are not, deliberation presupposes the very common ground it is invoked to generate.

I do not attempt to develop a full critique of deliberative democracy here, nor to adjudicate between alternative accounts of political legitimacy. The point is more limited but no less consequential: any theory that treats deliberation as operating over a shared space of reasons must either specify the semantic conditions under which that space exists or accept

real but meaningless for deliberative purposes: change the context slightly (religious exemptions from anti-discrimination law) and the frameworks diverge immediately. Overlapping consensus presupposes semantic stability in the ‘political’ domain that framework-relativity denies. Whether political concepts can maintain consistent meaning across comprehensive doctrines is precisely what this paper questions.

that its applicability is domain-restricted. Failing to do so risks mistaking a local success condition for a general political solution.²⁴

VI.4. For Political Practice

The implications for political practice follow directly from the preceding analysis and are, in a sense, already familiar – though rarely acknowledged at the appropriate level. Educational interventions aimed at correcting misinformation, fostering critical thinking, or encouraging epistemic openness will continue to disappoint, not because they are poorly designed or insufficiently resourced, but because they are misdirected. They target deliberative capacities downstream of the constraint they are meant to address.

Where political disagreement is structured by divergent semantic frameworks, appeals to better reasoning cannot do the work assigned to them. The agent is not failing to deliberate properly; they are deliberating competently within a grammar that determines what counts as relevant, what counts as evidence, and what counts as a legitimate conclusion. No amount of instruction in critical thinking can bridge a semantic gap that determines, in advance, what will even register as a candidate for critical assessment.

By contrast, the interventions that reliably *do* produce shifts in political response – strategic framing, control over formation environments, long-term immersion in particular linguistic practices – operate precisely at the level liberal political theory prefers not to acknowledge. These mechanisms do not refine deliberation; they structure the conditions under which deliberation becomes possible at all. They work not by persuading agents through reasons they already recognise, but by shaping the semantic field in which reasons come to be recognised in the first place.

This places liberal political practice in a persistent bind. The mechanisms that plausibly affect outcomes operate at a level that liberal norms tend to code as illegitimate:

²⁴ This argument has further implications for deliberative democracy, theories of political legitimacy, and accounts of public reason that I cannot pursue in this paper.

manipulation, propaganda, conditioning, or indoctrination. Meanwhile, the mechanisms liberalism endorses – education, dialogue, exposure to opposing views – operate at a level that is, in many cases, causally irrelevant to the persistence of disagreement. The problem is not hypocrisy or bad faith. It is a structural mismatch between the level at which change is possible and the level at which intervention is permitted.

Nothing in this diagnosis licenses a prescriptive conclusion about what *should* be done. That question would require normative commitments this paper does not attempt to supply. The point is more limited and more uncomfortable: standard political strategies fail not because political actors lack goodwill, intelligence, or sincerity, but because they are attempting to solve a semantic problem with deliberative tools. The constraint is semantic before it is political, and until that is acknowledged, political practice will continue to mistake predictable failure for contingent error.

VI.5. What This Isn't

Before closing, it is worth being explicit about several ways this argument is likely to be misread.

First, this is not cynicism. The claim is not that reasoning is futile, that dialogue is pointless, or that political disagreement is merely theatre. The claim is narrower and more precise: the primary constraint in cases of deep disagreement does not operate at the level of episodic deliberation. Identifying where a constraint operates is not a gesture of resignation; it is a condition of explanatory adequacy. To mislocate the constraint and then express disappointment when preferred remedies fail is not optimism but confusion.

Second, this is not relativism, at least not in the sense the charge usually presupposes. The accusation of relativism typically relies on a false dichotomy: either there are framework-transcendent standards of validity, or 'anything goes'. That dichotomy collapses once meaning is understood as practice-embedded. Ontological frameworks are not arbitrary, private, or subjective. They are stabilised through shared linguistic practices with determinate inferential roles, norms of correction, and patterns of salience. They are intersubjective, historically sedimented, and socially enforced. They are constrained – not by

an external tribunal of reason, but by pragmatic pressures operating at the level of practice formation and maintenance.

To say that validity is framework-relative is not to say that all frameworks are equally valid from nowhere. It is to say that 'validity' itself is a framework-internal notion. There is no external standpoint from which rival grammars can be ranked without remainder. This is not epistemic relativism; it is semantic realism. It takes seriously the claim, established in the philosophy of language, that meaning and normativity are constituted through use rather than grounded in a neutral semantic substrate.

Third, this is not quietism. The fact that the argument is diagnostic rather than prescriptive does not render it inert. Clarifying why certain interventions fail, where constraints actually operate, and which assumptions are doing illicit work is itself practically consequential. A diagnosis need not issue marching orders to alter the terrain on which future decisions are made. Refusing to offer a solution is not the same as denying that the problem matters.

Finally, this is not an anti-liberal polemic. The target is not liberal political commitments as such, but the semantic assumptions that liberal epistemology often treats as transparent: shared access to reasons, neutral diagnostic criteria, and deliberative revisability of framework-level commitments. Exposing those assumptions is not equivalent to rejecting liberalism as a political project. It is to show that certain liberal self-descriptions mischaracterise the mechanisms by which belief formation, disagreement, and persuasion actually occur.

The aim throughout has been deflationary rather than oppositional. No alternative political program is being smuggled in. No rival theory of justification is being advanced. The argument simply traces the consequences of taking the philosophy of language seriously where liberal epistemology would prefer not to. If the result is discomfort, that is not because the argument is radical, but because it removes a form of comfort liberal theory has come to rely on.

The account developed here is also empirically discriminable from standard liberal diagnoses. If disagreement reflects primarily agent-level epistemic failure, then improved deliberative conditions – extended reflection, access to counterevidence, epistemic incentives – should reliably produce convergence across frameworks. If, by contrast, constraint operates at the level of semantic intelligibility, then such interventions should yield intra-framework refinement without cross-framework convergence. The framing evidence presented in Section IV already supports the latter prediction: linguistic frame manipulation outperforms deliberative improvement in explaining response variance.²⁵ More systematic examination would test whether agents can accurately reconstruct opposing positions whilst nevertheless failing to recognise them as *reason-responsive* – indicating that the issue is not misunderstanding but incommensurable standards of reason-recognition. The framework advanced here does not evade empirical scrutiny. It predicts the systematic failures liberal epistemology has struggled to explain.

The account also makes a specific causal prediction about value formation. Liberal epistemology typically assumes that agents possess values which they then apply to determine what reasons count: values precede and structure ontological commitments. The present account reverses this ordering: ontological frameworks – the grammatical structures that determine what something *is* – precede and structure which values become salient.

Liberal Epistemology:

Values → Reasons → Beliefs

Present Account:

Ontology/Grammar → Salience → Values → Reasons → Beliefs

²⁵ Suggestive evidence for ontology-first development comes from research on early conceptual category formation (Carey 2009, *The Origin of Concepts*) and cross-cultural studies of moral development (Shweder et al. 1987). However, systematic testing of the causal ordering proposed here remains to be undertaken.

If this is correct, then shifting ontological framing (e.g., taxation as redistribution vs. seizure) should reliably shift which values apply (fairness vs. autonomy), whilst attempting to persuade through values alone, without altering ontological framing, should produce negligible effects across framework boundaries. This predicts that early-formed ontological categories will constrain subsequent value development more strongly than the reverse – a relationship that developmental and cross-cultural evidence could in principle discriminate.

VII. Conclusion

‘What we are destroying is nothing but houses of cards and we are clearing up the ground of language on which they stand’.

– Ludwig Wittgenstein, *Philosophical Investigations* (1953, §118)

VII.1. Summary of Argument

This paper has not disputed epistemology’s rational functions. Deliberation, justification, and epistemic evaluation all do real work within their proper domains.

What it has shown is that liberal epistemology’s semantic inputs – the background assumptions about shared access, neutral criteria, and deliberative revisability – are ill-typed for the problem domain. What follows is not irrationalism but a type error: applying deliberative remediation to semantic constraints yields outputs that are undefined relative to the phenomenon being addressed.²⁶ The program runs. The logic is valid. But it is answering a different question than the one it claims to answer. That is not a failure of reasoning. It is a failure of input specification.

²⁶The failure mode is analogous to feeding Unicode characters into a parser designed for ASCII. Within ASCII range, the parser functions correctly; outside that range, it produces artefacts that appear as gibberish. The error is not in the parser’s logic but in the mismatch between input specification and actual input structure. No amount of improved parsing will correct an encoding error. Colloquially, garbage in, garbage out.

Ranalli's framework presupposes semantic conditions that are unavailable given what the philosophy of language has already established. Shared access to reasons, neutral diagnostic criteria, and the deliberative revisability of framework-level commitments all require a neutral metalanguage from which those operations could be carried out. No such metalanguage exists. Meaning is practice-embedded, observation is theory-laden, and what counts as a reason is fixed by inferential roles internal to particular semantic grammars.

As a result, the diagnosis of indoctrination systematically mislocates constraint. What is treated as a failure at the level of agency – closed-mindedness, resistance to reasons, epistemic vice – is in fact a constraint operating at the level of semantic formation. Agents are not failing to reason properly; they are reasoning competently within grammars that make different considerations salient, different inferences natural, and different conclusions compelling.

This explains both the persistence of the phenomenon and the failure of the proposed remedies. Educational and deliberative interventions continue to target the agent's reasoning capacities because liberal epistemology has no conceptual resources for locating constraint elsewhere. When those interventions fail, the failure is attributed to insufficient education, poor implementation, or bad faith. But the error lies upstream. The deliberative machinery is being applied to a problem whose determining factors lie outside its domain of control.

Seen in this light, the distinction between education and indoctrination cannot be sustained on neutral grounds. Both operate through the shaping of semantic practices that determine what will later appear as obvious, reasonable, or compelling. What liberal theory codes as 'education' is ontology-formation it endorses; what it codes as 'indoctrination' is ontology-formation it rejects. The mechanism is the same. Only the evaluative stance differs.

VII.2. What the Diagnosis Shows

The conclusion to draw is not that deliberation is useless, that agency is illusory, or that disagreement is irresolvable. It is that liberal epistemology has overestimated what deliberation can do and underestimated the depth at which semantic formation operates.

Within shared frameworks, deliberation matters enormously. Epistemic virtues make a real difference. Careful reasoning outperforms sloppy reasoning. The model works often enough to appear universal. But when disagreement crosses framework boundaries, the same model becomes noise-amplifying. It mistakes semantic divergence for epistemic defect and treats consistency within an alien grammar as pathology.

This is why disputes of this kind exhibit such remarkable durability. Centuries of dialogue, education, and rational argument have not dissolved them – not because the participants are irrational, but because the constraints lie at a level those tools cannot reach. The expectation that they should dissolve is itself a grammatical artefact of liberal epistemology.

VII.3. The Withdrawal of an Assumption

This paper does not propose a new theory of indoctrination. It does not offer a rival account of justification, rationality, or political legitimacy. Its critical force lies elsewhere. It withdraws a background assumption that liberal epistemology has treated as cost-free.

Political philosophy has incorporated key results from the philosophy of language whilst declining to enforce their downstream consequences. It has accepted – often explicitly – the core lessons of Wittgenstein, Sellars, Quine, and Davidson: that meaning is use, that there is no epistemic given, that translation is underdetermined, that no neutral standpoint is available from which to adjudicate conceptual schemes. But it has rarely enforced the consequences of those commitments where they become most uncomfortable.

Once those debts are called in, liberal epistemology's approach to indoctrination cannot be sustained on its own terms. The assumptions of shared access to reasons, neutral diagnostic criteria, and deliberative revisability of framework-level commitments are not merely empirically fragile. They are semantically unavailable given the very theories of meaning liberal philosophy otherwise endorses.

The problem, then, is not that Ranalli's framework is politically objectionable, insufficiently progressive, or normatively suspect. It is that it presupposes a semantic architecture that cannot exist if the philosophy of language is taken seriously. The failure is

not ideological. It is structural. Liberal epistemology is asking deliberation to operate over materials that its own semantic commitments deny it access to.

VII.4. What Remains

With that assumption withdrawn, a familiar set of questions does not disappear, but it relocates.

If the constraints on belief, reasoning, and disagreement operate at the level of semantic formation rather than episodic deliberation, then meaningful intervention – where it is possible at all – will concern formation environments, institutional structures, and mechanisms of frame activation. These are the sites at which grammars are stabilised, salience is distributed, and inferential habits are sedimented over time.

This paper does not prescribe how such interventions ought to be designed, nor does it defend their legitimacy. It only marks the boundary of where liberal epistemology's preferred tools cannot reach. Appeals to education, critical thinking, and rational dialogue target a level of agency that is downstream of the operative constraints. Their persistent failure is not accidental, nor primarily moral. It is a predictable consequence of targeting the wrong variable.

None of this renders politics impossible. It renders it more constrained than liberal theory has typically allowed. Deliberation still matters. Agency still exists. Reasoning still does work. But not all the work, and not at all the levels we have asked it to perform.

What changes is not the necessity of political judgment, but the fantasy of a neutral semantic ground on which such judgment could finally be secured. Once that fantasy is relinquished, the task is no longer to perfect deliberative remedies for failures of understanding, but to reckon honestly with the conditions under which understanding is formed at all.

That reckoning lies beyond the scope of this paper. But the need for it does not.

VII.5. Final Note

Nothing in this argument requires rejecting liberal political commitments, nor does it mandate alternative institutional designs. Its force is diagnostic rather than prescriptive. It

shows that a theory of indoctrination built on assumptions of shared semantic access will necessarily misfire when those assumptions fail.

The uncomfortable implication is not that indoctrination cannot occur, but that liberal epistemology lacks the conceptual resources to diagnose it in the cases that matter most. Where semantic frameworks diverge, the language of epistemic vice becomes a projection rather than an explanation.

If that conclusion is resisted, it will not be because the reasoning here is unsound, but because accepting it would require liberal epistemology to acknowledge a limit it has long tried to deny: that deliberation does not stand outside language, and that the deepest conditions of intelligibility are not themselves available for neutral reflection.

That is not a moral failure or an epistemic one. It is a grammatical failure.

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